

A Framework For Indistinguishable Neurons Applied To Activation Functions

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Abstract

In the current model of artificial neural networks, individual neurons are distinguishable from within activation-space due to the directional dependence of many neural network functions. It is hypothesised that making neurons indistinguishable from within the space will improve the performance of networks by encouraging the collective behaviour of neurons. A set of criteria are outlined in this paper which propose a framework to ensure neuron indistinguishability for activation functions. Several new operations and activation functions are defined following this framework which are found to empirically support the hypothesis. Some functions utilising the indistinguishable neuron framework show a significant, accelerating reduction in training time with deeper neural networks which is contrary to typical network behaviour.

1 Introduction

1.1 A Spatial Intuition for Neural Networks

Exactly how each artificial neural network processes information can be difficult to interpret due to their potentially high complexity. However, an interpretation of imagining the network as a group of spatial transformations has had success in demystifying the actions of many artificial neural networks. This point of view is encouraged by the extensive use of matrix and tensor mathematics, which are commonly related to spatial systems. This spatial interpretation of networks is referred to as the *Manifold Hypothesis* [1].

Begin by indexing any specific neuron as k_i^t , where k represents the set of all neurons, t is the collection of neurons in a specific time-step of the network and i notates each individual neuron in the architecture such that every element is uniquely identified by i, t . We can define subsets of neurons (L_m) using two rules: the first is that all neurons in the subset must be independent of one another within the same time-step t - so no neurons interdepend within a subset. This is expressed in *Eqn. 1*. The second rule is that the subset should contain the maximum number of neurons possible which satisfy the previous rule.

$$(\forall i \neq j (k_i, k_j \in L_m), k_i^t \neq f(k_j^t, \dots)) \quad (1)$$

It can be shown that 'input neurons' always form a unique subset - however 'output neurons' and 'hidden neurons' not necessarily so. Using this definition the network can now be separated into subsets which can be called layers. These layers can then be ordered by their relative 'closeness' to the input layer. Often, the definition of layers are more arbitrary - simply an imposed organisational tool. Yet this can produce misleading connections such as 'sideways' connections and connections which appear to feed-back when they do not actually. This is demonstrated in *Fig. 1* - which is suggestive of feed-back connections despite being a purely feed-forward network. Using this more rigorous definition of a layer, described above, these misconception problems are resolved and the grouping of neurons into layers is less arbitrary and enables the spatial transformations to be defined consistently.

Figure 1: All the neuron connections in the above diagram are feed-forward connections. However, sometimes by using an arbitrary grouping of neurons into layers can result in misconceptions on how networks are operating. In the above diagram it may appear as if some connections go sideways and some feed-back - this is not actually the case. Fundamentally, there are only feed-forward, feed-back and terminating connections in any arbitrary neural network[2].

The manifold hypothesis begins by taking a layer of neurons and associating a space to this subset. The neurons in the layer can be used to create an orthonormal basis for the space. Hence, the space has an extrinsic dimensionality equal to the number of neurons in the layer. Consequently, this space is often called 'activation-space' or 'neuron-space', though we would propose 'qualia-space' may eventually be more appropriate (see *Sec. 1.2*).

Taking a dataset, each datapoint can be encoded in the activation of neurons. Activations of a specific neuron are scalar valued, so they can be represented by positions along the neuron's respective basis-vector. Taking a collection of neurons, the information they collectively encode can be represented by a coordinate in the space. Conversely, any datapoint in the space is a vector and can be decomposed into its constituent components along each neuron's

basis-vector - thus setting the activations of all the neurons for a particular datapoint. Hence, every datapoint can be represented by a coordinate point within space. When introducing many data points, from a real-world dataset, shapes are outlined by the position of these points. These shapes are referred to as manifolds, which are embedded in the space. Datasets are typically finite samples of all possible arrangements and hence are unlikely to be representative of the entire input domain. So these embedded manifolds are a sensible and common way to envisage the data.

Manifolds are then manipulated by the neural network using a variety of spatial transformations. These spatial transformations are performed on the space itself, yielding the next layer's space, thus the properties of the embedded manifolds are altered in the process. The fundamental action of all classification neural networks is to yield a more useful and interpretable manifold with specific features of the manifold more clearly expressed. To

The spatial transformations performed are often dependent upon the inter-connection weights between neurons as well as the type of neurons. Thus, the transformations are able to change until they produce quantitatively useful manifolds. Different network architectures, such as convolution and fully-connected, perform distinct types of transformations. To usefully extract data, transformations must locally reshape the manifold as opposed to global transformations such as rotation, scaling, shears and stretches.

Manifolds also have their own intrinsic dimensionality. We propose classifying transformations into three fundamental categories based on their effect on the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold:

- *Abstractive transformations* are those which tend to reduce the intrinsic dimensionality of a given manifold. These transformations can be qualitatively described as grouping related properties under a more general single classification - such as extracting the digit from an MNIST example[3]. Examples of abstractive transformations include Fully-connected network with fewer output neurons than the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold and usually convolutional neural networks. Concatenating recurrent neural networks can be shown to always be abstractive[2].
- *Reformative transformations* are those which tend to preserve the intrinsic dimensionality of a given manifold. These transformations can be thought to express all the same properties in a different way. In effect, expressing different properties of the same manifold. Matrix multiplications with a non-zero determinant are an example of a reformative transformation.
- *Generative transformations* are those which appear to increase the intrinsic dimensionality of a given manifold. These transformations can be thought to be attempting to restore detailed information from more general properties. Some deep-fully-connected neural networks with a greater number of output neurons than the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold coupled with specific activation functions (See *Sec. 2.1.5* and *Sec. 6.1.4*) may appear to be generative for sparse manifolds, however they

tend to embed information instead - preserving its intrinsic dimensionality. This is also the case for deconvolutional networks which appear to be generative but are instead a mapping of a low dimensional manifold (like an interpolatable memorisation). Methods of random vector generation from seed may be considered effectively generative.

Some transformations can be classified differently depending on the specific manifold and a specific locality. An example is the step-function, which is globally reformative but locally abstractive. Additionally, the overall type of transformation may be dependent on what transformations are considered as grouped together - for example a single neuron connection is never generative when considered in isolation. Therefore, this classification system should only be used on the layer system described above. These categories can be a useful way to express the relative change in the quality of data between two locations in a network.

Although the manifold hypothesis is now widespread, it is still common for more emphasis to be placed on the behaviour of individual neurons rather than the collective behaviour of their layer. This is apparent in activation functions which are often applied elementwise - thus treating neurons individually rather than considering their group behaviour. The overall aim of this paper is for the general distribution of a manifold to not be distorted depending on the specific direction of the neuron basis vectors. This would make it impossible to isolate the direction of a single neuron from within the space. Since one cannot separate out individual neuron directions, the network is expected to behave as collectively as possible. Treating neurons individually has potentially limited the effectiveness of many activation functions, as this group behaviour has been neglected. Therefore, a set of criteria have been compiled which should improve the performance of activation functions particularly when they are applied to groups of neurons. These criteria are also tailored for generally reformative and abstractive very-deep neural networks.

1.2 Origin-Centricity Postulate

(Some rudimentary results are included in this section, as opposed to the main results section later, due to this discussion being a tangential topic to the paper.)

Neural networks act to manipulate the distribution of data manifolds in activation space. The origin-centricity postulate is, most generally, a statement that the functions used in a neural network should be consistently centred. For artificial neural networks, in their current form, this centering should be about the origin. This is expected to allow networks to more easily transform and separate out important features. Without a consistent centre to transformations, an uncontrolled directional preference to manifolds may develop parallel or orthogonal to the line(s) between different transformation centres - this may bias the network in interpreting a manifold. This postulate is used to reason several optimisations to activation functions. The proposition remains as a postulate as it is only testable for specific activation functions but is suspected to be more generally valid for networks.

Many functions used in neural networks can already be considered origin-centric: their transformations having a unique behaviour about the origin. This can include changing the transformation's behaviour at or across the origin (such as in ReLU and its variants). A non-identity matrix multiplication leaves coordinates at the origin unchanged whilst the rest of the space is scaled towards or away from the origin depending on the specific matrix and direction. A further example is elementwise-multiplication: when either input vector is equal to $\vec{0}$ then the function always produces $\vec{0}$ - hence a unique outcome at the origin. There are many exceptions to this rule, particularly elementwise-addition which translates all space evenly including the origin. This, coupled with a matrix multiplication produces an *affine transformation* where the 'centre' of the transformation is arbitrary. However, offsetting the manifold from the origin is a process used to transform between primary meaning-bases which are an intrinsic coordinate system for the manifold. Nevertheless, on initialisation of a network, these transformations often begin as origin-centric due to a zero-initialised bias.

For a neural network to manipulate a given data manifold in a useful way requires reshaping of that manifold. To reshape a manifold, the transformation must act to translate distinct areas of the manifold differently. If all areas are translated evenly, then the manifold is not reshaped but instead is translated - this is occasionally required but in isolation does not tend to transform the manifold usefully. Under most neural network non-linear operations, regions relatively close together get transformed the same way, thus if the manifold occupies a very small volume it tends to not be reshaped much.

When considering a linear operation followed by an activation function, in general, the potential for manifold distortion is maximised when the manifold subtends a larger angle from the origin. This is clearer in a ReLU function and its (non-Geebs) variants where the distortion is already directional. It is hypothesised that network operations which encourage this distribution, around a consistent centre, allow the network to more effectively reshape the manifold, ascertaining its important features. Thus better performance would be expected for the optimised functions which enable this distribution prior to further transformations. This proposition is also encouraged by the success of batch-normalisation, which standardises the manifold to be about the origin. In *Sec. 2.1.7*, the postulate is used to suggest that activation functions should have the centre of their output space at the origin. This notion can also be used to indicate the validity of the origin-centricity postulate by sliding the centre of an activation function's output space by various amounts whilst measuring the performance of the resulting network. A 'sliding-activation-function' is described in *Eqn. 2*, which is the standard elementwise Sigmoid with a term for sliding the function in the $\hat{1}$ direction. The performance of a network, for different amounts of sliding, is displayed in *Fig. 2* using *Eqn. 2*.

This is an indirect method to test the postulate as any activation function imposes its own regime onto the network's distribution of manifolds - so cannot be extrapolated to the general case. The postulate may be validated if a general fit can be found for *Fig. 2*, *Fig. 3* and other sliding activation functions. This

general fit must then be extrapolated to no activation function and if it is observed that the resulting accuracy is maximised around the origin, this would confirm the postulate for the general network.

Figure 2: Shows a modified version of elementwise Sigmoid, where the centre of space is shifted by α in the $\vec{1}$ direction. For every datapoint, 5 repeats were collected. The accuracy was determined after 2500 epochs, tested on an unseen MNIST test set. Finer interval tests were performed near key features of the trend. The network consisted of a convolutional and fully-connected network architecture. The network did not utilise batch-normalisation as this would have affected the offset.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \alpha \vec{1} + \sum_i \frac{\hat{e}_i}{1 + e^{-x_i}} \quad (2)$$

It can be seen in *Fig. 2* that the accuracy of the network is maximised roughly between $-0.80 < \alpha < 0.00$, where $\alpha = -0.50$ corresponds to the origin-centric version of Sigmoid - since Sigmoid is usually centred at 0.5 . This result suggests that the origin-centricity postulate is valid for a Sigmoid network as the accuracy is maximised roughly about the offset $\alpha = -0.40$ which is closer to the origin. Therefore, the network performs better when the centre of the activation function's output space is roughly closest to the origin. This is corroborated by *Fig. 3*, where an analogous experiment is performed for the Gees-Tanh function shown in *Sec. 3.2*.

Figure 3: Shows a modified version of Geesbs-Tanh, where the centre of space is shifted by α in the $\bar{1}$ direction. For every datapoint, 5 repeats were collected. The accuracy was determined after 2500 epochs, tested on an unseen MNIST test set. A more symmetric trend is seen about the origin in this figure. An identical network architecture was utilised - only the activation function was changed.

This postulate can also provide an interpretation of how neural networks tend to spatially organise a manifold. In most applications neural networks isolate datapoints dependent upon the different abstract properties they represent. Considering this, and that networks attempt to reshape manifolds to separate out different useful features, it is proposed that a network will tend to produce a distribution where different unique properties of the manifold are represented as specific directions about the space’s centre. In the case of artificial neural networks the centre is the origin. This is the property-direction hypothesis which maximises the network’s potential to separate out useful features. These features are typically different qualitative properties of the data. Networks are expected to achieve the property-direction distribution by reshaping specific trend-curves of the initial manifold to be linear and origin centric (discussed further in *Sec. 2.1.5*). Thus, making it easier for future (predominantly linear) transformations to extrapolate and interpolate trends. Accordingly, it should be found that datapoints representing similar meanings are found close to the same specific direction whereas different concepts have their own unique direction. However, these ‘meanings’ or properties may not necessarily align with distinctions humans would make in the same data.

This interpretation is not novel, with individual neurons being assigned to specific meanings [4]. However, this modified interpretation suggests it is the basis-vectors for the intrinsic coordinate system of the manifold which should be assigned meanings as opposed to the neuron-basis for the activation-space. This is due to the manifold often being a lower dimensional embedding of information, so it is not sensible to assume every neuron is representative of a

unique meaning nor that meanings should be neuron-basis aligned. Henceforth, the basis spanning the manifold will be referred to as the meaning-basis to draw distinction between the coordinate system of the activation space.

Further discussion on the property-direction interpretation can be found in *Sec. 6.1.2*. Distributions from an auto-encoder and classification network are compared in the section and it is found that there is a tendency of property-directions to become orthogonal. This observed orthogonality leads to the second spatial interpretation from the origin-centricity postulate, the 'signed-strength-scaling interpretation'. This interpretation explains why the directions are closer to orthogonal rather than in opposite directions, which would otherwise surround the origin further. The interpretation states that: as the strength of a property increases, so does its respective datapoint's magnitude from the origin in the direction representing that property and a change in a scaling's sign indicates the opposite property.

This signed-strength-scaling interpretation follows from the previous property-direction interpretation: if directions from the origin indicate the presence of a property in the data, then a point with no direction possesses no properties. The only point with undefined direction from the origin is the origin itself. Consequently, in this interpretation, the origin (or centre of the space) represents a datapoint with no properties. Networks are not necessarily perfect at grouping data that humans would deem similar, therefore it might be observed that human defined properties seem to be represented in a general direction as opposed to an exact one for an observer. Yet, the network's meaning-basis would still be considered specific but less clearly distinguishable to an observer. It would be observed that as the magnitude decreases the overlap of otherwise distinguishable properties occurs due to those properties being only represented in an apparent general direction. Thus, datapoints at small magnitudes, in an imperfect network, may have poorer isolation of their true intended properties. Hence, datapoints around the origin tend to have less distinguished distribution, leading to the origin having no property at all. This description may also produce an origin which represents all properties, although there are points in activation space already representing this case and these are found in the $\hat{1}$ direction with respect to the meaning-basis according to the property-direction interpretation. This leads back to the origin continuing to represent no properties when both interpretations are considered simultaneously. Another argument is that there must be a crossover point, between the properties being represented, when travelling from any one direction to the origin then from the origin to any other direction. This crossover point must be the origin when considering every permutation of directions.

Some intuitions lend themselves to these interpretations. Considering datapoints as representing a property with an associated strength - i.e. [bright]-[blue] ([strength]-[property]). It is natural for the property to exhibit a modular behaviour but not a strength. If 'blue' and 'green' are orthogonal unit vectors one can continuously rotate through all angles, in their plane, with the resulting vector representing a sensible composite colour of the same strength. Whilst strength may be considered a scalar so does not exhibit this behaviour. Like-

wise, considering the MNIST dataset, you may find a '1' which appears like a '2', '3' or a '4' etc. potentially for all permutations. The natural way to represent this is if the properties are represented as directions. Further, operations such as a single dot-product, such as in a many-to-one fully connected network or single convolution, can be interpreted as finding the component of a datapoint in a specified direction - or how much of a property that datapoint represents. Thus convolutions and matrix-multiplications can be considered to change from a basis representing one set of properties as directions to another set of properties in directions.

Moreover, presenting the negative of the stimuli will produce a response equal and opposite to the initial response in the activations of the input layer, with respect to the space's centre. Thus, the direction is opposite, but the magnitude (or strength of the properties) is the same. This is the least abstract inverse stimuli for the least abstract layer. If the same effect is to be achieved in a deeper layer then a more abstract definition of the inverse stimuli may need to be presented. Consequently, opposite directions can be interpreted as representing opposite properties as perceived by the network - analogous to antonyms. The 'signed' term refers to this phenomena and the term 'perceived' is not meant to have any connotation to awareness nor consciousness. This interpretation would explain why the similarity matrix presented in *Sec. 6.1.2* classifies different digits close to orthogonally rather than opposite, as they are not of opposite meaning as perceived by the network (nor to a human observer for this case). It also explains why the classification network, presented in the same section, utilised just one hemisphere in *Fig. 31*. It is also important to establish that every artificial network layer will produce its own meaning-basis when trained, the same basis is unlikely to be used throughout all layers and previously used basis will become distorted in following layers. Networks act to produce increasingly useful meaning-bases - such as a classification network which would be expected to assign increasingly abstract concepts along its meaning-bases. Thus, the inverse stimulus is dependent on the layer being considered.

It can then be reasoned that if negative scaling (opposite direction) is indicative of the opposite property, whilst the origin represents no property and positive scaling indicates the property, then it is hypothesised that the signed-scaling is indicative of a property's strength. Thus, increasing the scaling in a particular direction indicates the increasing strength of that property represented in that direction - or components of properties if the direction can be broken down into more distinct property-directions. Further, a negative scaling represents the presence of an opposite property as perceived by the network. This signed-strength-scaling interpretation is also supported by the choice of some activation functions, such as sigmoid, which saturate at large magnitudes. The property-direction and signed-strength-scaling interpretations don't contradict the established understanding on the manifold hypothesis, they provide a further method to rationalise the observed manifold distributions. An intuitive example of the interpretations is discussed in *Sec. 6.1.1*.

The property-direction and signed-strength-scaling interpretations are descriptions of how the network represents its data, though they may be used as a

predictive tool only when alignment is expected between how humans perceive stimuli and how the network represents them. Such as in the case of digit appearance and the imposed digit classifications discussed in *Sec. 6.1.2*. It is not expected that correlation will always be found between the distinct features humans have defined and those which an unbiased network defines. Nevertheless the interpretation can be insightful in either case.

These interpretations construct a non-orthonormal 'meaning-basis' for the manifold, where the respective vectors are representative of unique, abstract properties behind the data - usually they consist of the properties most significant to the network's aim. A meaning-basis can be considered the effective coordinate system for the intrinsic manifold at a particular layer whereas the neuron-basis is the natural coordinate system of the extrinsic activation space at a particular layer - where both are specified by the network's parameters and structure respectively. For a trained network, the meaning-bases for each layer are also expected to follow the origin-centricity postulate, hence they are expected to be origin-centric and linear. Although all directions may be indicative of properties in the data, they can all be considered combinations of these primary meaning-basis-vectors chosen as the most distinct by the observer. We propose the property-directions are correlated with experience *for that specific layer*, as suggested in *Sec. 6.1.2* by the distinctions between digit appearances. Thus, all directions indicate specific experiences resulting in opposite directions also being experienced as different sensations. Using this, datapoints can then be broken down into individual components along these meaning-basis-vectors indicating a relative strength of each primary 'experience' for that datapoint - thus a mapping between 'experience' and neuron activations can be found. This is more flexible and favourable to assuming important meanings are always neuron-basis aligned - especially when the manifold is of lower intrinsic dimension than the activation-space. This distribution is valid for the final layer of a classification network as it is imposed by the user to make the manifold interpretable. In this case the meaning-basis is equal to the neuron-basis. As a network trains, the transformations will shift to minimise cost, this will yield a changing meaning-basis which following layers will have to adjust to reinterpret the meaning.

A caveat is that finding which directions the specific meaning-basis-vectors point in is troublesome and to some degree arbitrary - especially with the spherically symmetric 'Geebs functions' resulting in indistinguishable neuron-basis-vectors. The meaning-basis is simply an interpretive tool, which an observer may assign their own unique meanings to, but to a network is unintentional and merely reflects important distinctions in the data. Nevertheless, we propose that for a conscious being qualia are very strongly correlated to, or even equivalent to, these meaning-bases when the correct grouping of neurons is considered - since a layer is not as well defined in biological networks. Thus, we expect specific qualia to be represented directionally with a magnitude in accordance with the property-direction and signed-strength-scaling interpretations. This is discussed further in *Sec. 6.1.3*.

Current batch-normalisation (Batch-Norm) [5], which happens to also as-

sume origin-centricity, is classically thought to improve the performance of networks by reducing covariate shift. However, the Batch-Norm transformation changes the direction of vectors. This is unproblematic if it is a consistent change, such as with a very large batch, as the following network layer will compensate for the change and may be used to reshape the manifold usefully. Yet, inconsistency may mean the network confuses one property for another. Our next paper will examine whether a modified version of batch-normalisation, which instead standardises the magnitudes so that it is more in alignment with the origin-centricity postulate, leads to any further improvement in network performance.

2 Function Criteria

2.1 Greater Criteria

Greater criteria are criteria which the functions should follow to be effectively optimised - they are considered more crucial than lesser criteria. Yet, the ordering of greater criteria is not indicative of their relative importance. The criteria are not believed to be an exhaustive list; further advancements in understanding the spatial nature of networks will likely reveal some further optimisations to activation functions.

2.1.1 Non-Linear Function

For any fully-connected neural network with a linear activation function (or no activation function at all), the neural network consists of a series of linear transformations only. Thus, the entire network's function could be summarised as a single fully-connected-layer - lacking the complex information processing which makes these networks particularly useful. Analogous arguments can be made for all other types of artificial neural networks. Non-linearity allows for local transformations to the shape of a manifold. Therefore, the first criterion is that the activation function must be non-linear. All widely used activation functions meet this criterion. It is an essential condition if one wishes to build a network capable of recognising anything more than linear trends. *Eqn. 3* expresses this criterion mathematically, where $\vec{F}(\vec{x})$ is henceforth the activation function.

$$(\exists \vec{p} \cap \exists i \cap \exists j), \left(\frac{\partial^2 \vec{F}(\vec{x})_i}{\partial \vec{x}_j^2} \Big|_{\vec{p}} \neq 0 \right) \quad (3)$$

2.1.2 Utilise Multi-Variable Input

The premise for this paper is to consider neurons collectively rather than place more emphasis on their individual behaviours. Therefore, when designing activation functions, the aim should be to ensure the function makes suitable use of

all input variables. Consequently, where appropriate, the Jacobian associated with the function should contain non-zero off-diagonal elements. However, this should not be done haphazardly without suitable reason. With off-diagonal elements equal to zero, it is an elementwise function, therefore the image of the input space through the function is hyper-cubic. This leads to uneven distribution of the manifolds (See *Sec. 2.1.4*) and may mean further spatial transformations are less efficient at isolating useful information in the manifold. Consequently, networks would need to be made larger to achieve comparable performance. *Eqn. 4* is an expression summarising this criterion.

$$\sum_{i \neq j} \left| \frac{\partial \vec{F}(\vec{x})_i}{\partial \vec{x}_j} \right| > 0 \quad (4)$$

This criterion is implied by the spherically symmetric criterion in *Sec. 2.1.4*, but if spherical symmetry is not possible such as in *Sec. 3.4* then the multi-variable criteria should be met instead. Softmax is an example of one of the few common activation function to utilise a multivariate input, and hence apply its transformation collectively.

2.1.3 Preservation of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Dimensionality

The intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold should not change drastically from the input to the output of the function. Hence, activation functions should always aim to be reformative. Removing a dimension results in the uncontrolled loss of information and adding a dimension causes overhead. The intrinsic dimensionality is allowed to vary slightly as this can be advantageous for generative processes (See *Sec. 2.1.5* and *Sec. 6.1.4*).

Many existing functions conform to this criterion, however, softmax and the step function do not. Softmax reduces the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold by collapsing the manifold to a bounded hyper-plane. The extrinsic dimensionality is unaffected by softmax. The step-function is an edge case for this criterion; the extrinsic and global intrinsic dimensionality is preserved, but the intrinsic dimensionality is not preserved locally as the manifold is collapsed to singular points. These singular points can be indexed by integer, thus the resultant manifold can be represented using one scalar value. *Figure 4* shows how manifolds are collapsed onto a bounded plane by softmax and to singular points by the step function.

Figure 4: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Centre) shows the image of the input space through a softmax mapping. It can be observed that softmax reduces the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold, in this case to \mathbb{R} whilst preserving the extrinsic dimensionality. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a step-function mapping. The step function also violates the criterion as the intrinsic dimensionality is not preserved locally, in effect the manifold is partitioned into smaller unconnected manifolds. The software Desmos [15] was used to produce all function graphics in this paper. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/wybyi4a81o>.

Despite this, step-functions and softmax have features which make them desirable in specific use cases. This includes human-network interfaces such as the output layer of the network, as no further manifold transformations are taking place, so it is acceptable to lose some seemingly redundant data. For example, in many networks the output manifold needs to be distributed in a way that is easily interpretable by humans; this is enabled by softmax. A network will likely learn to counteract this uncontrolled loss of information by manipulating the manifold to preserve its most important properties - though this is not ideal as it may extend the training time for the network. The step-function is useful in networks utilising boolean activations.

Finally, softmax also finds uses inside networks - such as transformer networks[6]. These are examples of *specific* use cases for softmax - so these *generalised* activation function criteria do not apply. Apart from exceptions like these, softmax would produce a sub-optimal distribution of the manifold for the network.

Eqn. 5 and *Eqn. 6* express the preservation of the intrinsic and extrinsic dimensionalities respectively. Where \vec{a}_i is an activation vector and $\{\vec{a}_i, \dots\}$ is a collection of activation vectors in a manifold:

$$In(\{\vec{a}_1, \vec{a}_2, \dots, \vec{a}_i\}) \simeq In\left(\left\{\vec{F}(\vec{a}_1), \vec{F}(\vec{a}_2), \dots, \vec{F}(\vec{a}_i)\right\}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\dim(\vec{a}_i) = \dim\left(\vec{F}(\vec{a}_i)\right) \quad (6)$$

2.1.4 Spherically Symmetric

Any asymmetries result in the uneven distribution of manifolds, as certain regions of space become more and less favourable to store manifolds. This can be beneficial as more non-linear zones are introduced, however careless asymmetries may be detrimental to a network's performance. Thus, by introducing symmetries, the activation space becomes more even and has potentially better

suited probabilities to store manifolds. The property-direction interpretation states that directions are generally representative of different properties found in the dataset (see *Sec. 1.2*). Thus, there should be no bias towards any directions as this would distort the manifold in favour of certain properties, in an uncontrolled way. Therefore a useful symmetry is the spherical-symmetry of a transformation, such that the function performed is independent of the input vector’s direction. This enables a roughly even, hyper-spherical manifold distribution about the origin, whereas an elementwise activation function would produce a hyper-cubic output space as shown in *Fig. 8*. This criterion would further encourage an origin-centric distribution which is postulated to be beneficial. By introducing a spherical symmetry about the origin, the available space which manifolds can occupy is also increased, since all directions are equally favourable. This may increase the potential for the network to usefully reshape the manifold and potentially allow a broader scope of properties to be expressed at each layer of the neural network. This should result in an improved training rate since the network is able to more easily tease out important features of the manifold.

The mention of more available activation-space is not an assertion that activation functions which result in a bounded output space are bad, due to their reduced space, only that their finite bounds need to be equidistant from the centre of the output space in all directions to ensure maximisation of available angular space. The criterion is referring to the activation function’s transformation being spherically symmetric, however this happens to imply a hyper-spherical activation space too. In terms of the resultant activation space, it can be seen that a hyper-cubic space produces favoured directions as the bounding of the space and the form of the jacobian at a coordinate are direction dependent. This must introduce a bias towards certain directions resulting in some features of the data being interpreted better than others.

Moreover, the importance of neurons acting as a collective has already been emphasised - this is the foundational reason for the success of deep learning as a whole. As stated, an activation space is parameterised by coordinates representing the individual activations of neurons in a layer. By introducing a spherical symmetry about the origin of the space it is then not possible to identify the direction of these neuron-basis-vectors from an observer inside the space - only the origin is identifiable by observing the distribution of manifolds. Therefore, the general manifold distribution becomes independent of the coordinate system used, with the exception of the origin. It may be reasoned that allowing this symmetry may increase the collective behaviour of neurons, as no neuron is individually distinguishable, whilst the layer still retains its previous functionality. This more unified behaviour, instead of the cumulative action of independent neurons, would be a preferable property for new activation functions. This begins the indistinguishable neuron framework. Hence, the spherically symmetric criterion is defined, resulting in no unfavourable direction for the distribution of manifolds. *Eqn. 7* describes this criterion, where henceforth $\mathbf{R} \in SO(n)$ for a layer of n neurons and \vec{a} is a constant vector offset which is allowed to take any value to fulfill the criteria, both \mathbf{R} and \vec{a} must be constant for all \vec{x} .

$$\mathbf{R}(\vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{a}) = \vec{F}(\mathbf{R}\vec{x}) + \vec{a} \quad (7)$$

A convenient way of producing such a function is by having a function of only the magnitude of a datapoint, φ , multiplied by a unit direction. The magnitude functions is shown in *Eqn. 8*:

$$|\vec{F}(\vec{x})| \equiv \varphi(|\vec{x}|) \cap \varphi\left(\left|\frac{\vec{x}}{|\vec{x}|}\right|\right) = 0 \quad (8)$$

With use of this criterion there is, in effect, no longer anything special about individual neurons besides the way we notate the mathematical computations. We are unaware of any widely used activation functions that currently possess this indistinguishable property. *Fig. 5* shows an example of some current activation functions.

Figure 5: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Centre) shows the image of the input space through a Sigmoid mapping. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Leaky-ReLU mapping. It can be observed that Sigmoid, and Leaky-ReLU do not possess a spherical symmetry. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/wybyi4a81o>.

Both ReLU and Leaky-ReLU are unbounded but do collapse and scale only in certain directions respectively. ReLU retains 2^{-d} (where d is the extrinsic dimension) of the initial scalable directions available in the input space. Thus, introducing strongly favoured encoding directions. Sigmoid and Tanh operate on each point's vector components, consequently creating a hyper-cubic space. Hence, the distance from the centre to the boundary of the output space is dependent on direction. According to this argument, networks so far have been performing sub-optimally with an effective loss in how much information can be encoded by a set of neurons. The majority of activation functions are applied elementwise so the layer's collective behaviour is not considered. Applying the indistinguishable activation functions elementwise would yield a neuron-distinguishable framework.

2.1.5 Projection

There are many ways in which a spherically-symmetric function could be created. One could imagine taking a \mathbb{R}^2 input space and wrapping distant regions

into an infinitely thin spiral pattern - creating a whirlpool-like spherically-symmetric bounded output space shown in *Fig. 6*. This function fulfils all criteria so far, but would likely produce a poorly performing network.

Figure 6: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, in red are a set of arbitrary lines following the form $y = mx$. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a made-up whirlpool mapping. It can be observed that the whirlpool mapping causes a rotational-skew to the previously linear lines passing through the origin - thus does not fulfil the projection criterion.

The initial dataset will contain many abstract properties and for each data-point in the set these properties will have specific magnitudes e.g. one image may be brighter than another - where brightness would be the property. The dataset manifold will be shaped by these properties; a specific property will change strength along a certain curve through the manifold and it is likely that these trend-curves are not linear to begin with. A classification network's purpose is to express only the important properties by manipulating these trend-curves to become linear in space and interpretable to people. Usually for the output of a classifier network we want these trend-lines to become neuron-basis aligned, so that one neuron-basis-vector corresponds to the strength of only one property.

Continuing with the origin-centricity postulate, networks are composed of operations of which many are origin-centric and linear. Therefore, it is conjectured that it is beneficial to the network if these important trend-curves are reshaped into linear trend-lines. This would make small changes to activations more interpretable to following layers. It would then be advantageous to keep the important trends linear throughout the following network's spatial transformations, such that once an important meaning-basis-vector is established it can be kept through the following meaning-bases. This is so that the network can more easily manipulate the properties rather than having to repeatedly re-linearise the trends after uncontrolled distortion by the activation function before it can usefully transform them again. Without this, needless re-linearisation of trend-lines wastes transformations (and training time) or alternatively the network has to learn a more complicated representation of the data to account for the trend-curves (increasing training time). The network could otherwise be doing something productive to the manifold.

If an activation function causes a rotational skew with increasing vector magnitudes then any trend-lines which the network has attempted to make linear and origin-centric are once again distorted and the network would have to use further transformations to continually correct for this. If the skew is slight and the data sparse, the network may assume that a property increases in a certain direction when it does not - resulting in the network failing to extrapolate principles as it will assume the trend remains linear as observed near the origin. In effect, if the space curves so do the meaning-basis-vectors. Furthermore, this can cause a property to begin to cross over into a direction ordinarily considered as a different property - causing the network to wrongly interpret its meaning as something else as it has failed to correct for the distortion.

The curving of the original linear lines can be observed in *Fig. 5* in the centre Sigmoid mapping; here the origin-centric green lines bend towards the corners of the space. If the network accounts for the curving, it has dedicated more neurons to interpret the more complicated representation. In addition, this will also still extrapolate poorly as the network is using mostly linear algebra to approximate these curves. The curving is needless and potentially detrimental, requiring more time for the network to learn and reduces the effective network's processing power on the input data. These problems can be avoided by ensuring that vectors through the origin remain linear.

This criterion can be summarised as: points on a line drawn through the centre of the input space should all remain on another line drawn through the centre of the output space. It does not matter if all the input lines are rotated evenly about this centre during the activation function, however there is no clear purpose to do so. In summary, the direction must not be dependent on the distance of a point from the centre of the space. *Eqn. 9* expresses this criterion mathematically:

$$\hat{x} = \mathbf{R} \frac{\vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{a}}{|\vec{F}(\vec{x}) + \vec{a}|} \quad (9)$$

This criterion can be met by having a function of the vector's direction, ϕ , multiplied by a magnitude. The functions of the direction is described in *Eqn. 10*:

$$\arg \vec{F}(\vec{x}) \equiv \phi(\arg \vec{x}) \quad (10)$$

Eqn. 11 consolidates the projection and spherical symmetry criteria into one expression. The simplest way to ensure these criteria are met is if the function consists of a unit-length direction (\hat{x}) and a magnitude function ($\varphi(|\vec{x}|)$).

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \phi(\hat{x}) \varphi(|\vec{x}|) \rightarrow \varphi(|\vec{x}|) \hat{x} \quad (11)$$

The origin-centricity postulate may not always be valid for an arbitrary network. However, non-linearities must be introduced to the activation function somewhere and due to the spherical symmetry criterion then there is an enforced centre to the space with the non-linearity being isotropic - we choose this to be

the origin in the neuron-basis. If beneficial, the network should just migrate manifolds such that the origin-centricity postulate is fulfilled for the meaning-basis too. However, the inability to keep non origin-intersecting lines straight may actually be advantageous if generative transformations are required. This is discussed further in *Sec. 6.1.4*.

Finally, some functions such as the 'min' and 'max' function appear to follow the projection criterion, yet on the boundary of the output space the projection criterion is not fulfilled as shown in *Fig. 7*. This is a problem as once again the network may assume that along a certain direction a quantity increases. However, if a value surpasses the cutoff it begins to trace along the boundary - thus the direction is changing with increasing magnitude of that property. Moreover, the network cannot compensate for this, by re-linearisation, as information is lost on the boundary. Thus, the network cannot tell what the magnitude should have been; therefore cannot figure out the original direction and hence the relative components of the meaning-basis-vector it belonged to. This is the 'refractive problem', described by the changing of the direction of a straight line at or past a boundary, where the original line passed through the space's centre. To remedy this issue, *Eqn. 27* can be used as a suitable replacement for many min and max operations where a cut-off box is needed.

Figure 7: Green is originally a straight-infinite line in the input space \mathbb{R}^2 . (Left) shows an image of the input space through a min-max box function, $f(x) = \max(-1, \min(x, 1))$, which clips the length of the line when it exceeds the bounding cube centred on the origin. It can be observed that there is a trailing line which follows the boundary, thus not fulfilling the projection criterion. (Right) shows a modified function (described in *Sec. 3.4*) which corrects the box function so that it does not leave a trailing edge - thus fulfilling the projection criterion. Neither example fulfils the spherical symmetry criterion, nevertheless can be useful in some *specific* circumstances. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/morbsp9v1n>.

In summary: by ensuring that all points on the same centred line remain on another centred line after the transformation, then the meaning-basis-vectors should remain linear as they are assumed to be origin-centric. The presence of a linear meaning-basis means that the network can more easily extrapolate trends and that these trends are more interpretable as the network does not need to perform extra processing to account for more complicated curved trend-lines.

The network can then reason that along the trend-line a property in the data gets stronger. All of this results in the output space being a spherical projection of the input space.

2.1.6 Presence of an Identity Jacobian

It is also important for the activation function to have the magnitude of a derivative of one somewhere in its domain, preferably at the origin. It should also contain no derivatives with a magnitude greater than one. This is to ease the potential problem of vanishing and exploding gradients in very-deep neural networks. If an activation function had a maximum magnitude of a derivative less than one ($|d_x| < 1$), then repeated applications of the function cause the gradient to become increasingly smaller, eventually tending to zero: $|d_x|^\infty = 0$. Thus, the vanishing gradient problem arises for a deep network. If $|d_x| > 1$ then $|d_x|^\infty = \infty$ which is the exploding gradient problem.

Further, if a function is to be scaled to meet this criterion, it should not be done in a manner such as the following: $\vec{f}(\vec{x}) \rightarrow \vec{f}(a\vec{x})$ where $a \in \mathbb{R}$. This is because the network's weights will shift to counteract this change, so the scaling will be ineffective.

Overall, the Jacobian of the activation functions at some location (\vec{p}) should be the identity matrix - this ensures spherical symmetry. However, this identity matrix can be rotated to any arbitrary angle in accordance to the spherical symmetry criterion, thus is multiplied by a matrix of the orthogonal group: $\mathbf{A} \in O(n)$ such that $\det(\mathbf{A}) = \pm 1$. Eqn. 12 and 13 are mathematical descriptions of this criterion where $J_f(\vec{p})$ is the jacobian of the activation function evaluated at position \vec{p} and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

$$\left(\vec{p} \approx \vec{0} \cap \mathbf{A} \in O\left(\dim\left(\vec{F}(\vec{x})\right)\right)\right), (J_f(\vec{p}) = \mathbf{AI}) \quad (12)$$

$$(\forall \vec{p}), (|\det(J_f(\vec{p}))| \leq 1) \quad (13)$$

We can assume that an untrained network has activation values statistically distributed around the origin, therefore the most likely activation is unchanged by the activation function if the gradient of one is at the origin. Consequently when propagating back errors, the activation function does not cause the errors to becoming increasingly large or small which would otherwise reduce learning deeper into the neural network after it has just been initialised.

This does not eliminate an issue we call '*gradient dilution*' which is described by the gradients becoming increasingly 'averaged out' deep into a network. The result is that many neurons deep in the network learn to respond to similar stimuli rather than diversifying - thus making needless redundancy. This is a direct consequence of little significant difference between each neuron's learning gradient so they effectively get trained to behave the same. This is what we call top-down learning where the output layers learn more specific unique behaviour before the hidden layers closer to the input.

2.1.7 Centre at the Origin

Non-linear, spherically symmetric functions by definition have a unique centre. Due to the origin-centricity postulate it is suggested that the centre of the output space of an activation function is at the origin with respect to the neuron-basis-vectors. As mentioned, the origin-centricity postulate infers the property-direction and signed-strength-scaling hypotheses (See *Sec. 1.2*).

If the output space of an activation function is not centred on the origin the relative directions to regions of the manifold are not preserved (as the meaning basis is shifted off the origin). This may cause the network to mistakenly classify some regions of the manifold as more similar than they are when other origin-centric functions continue to be used. As stated, the origin-centricity postulate also infers that the network classifies opposite directions as opposite properties in the activation space. If two such vectors ($\vec{x}_1 = \hat{1}$ and $\vec{x}_2 = -\hat{1}$) are imaged under the Sigmoid mapping ($S(\vec{x})$) then their resultant images under Sigmoid are in the same direction from the origin ($S(\vec{x}_1) = aS(\vec{x}_2)$ where ($a > 0$)) - this is an issue under the assumption of the origin-centricity postulate. To the network, this would indicate the vectors convey the same property at different strengths. Affine transformations could resolve this issue by centering the manifold back onto the origin, yet this would require otherwise unnecessary transformations and therefore training time. Results presented already in *Sec. 1.2* support this criterion. *Eqn. 14* describes this criterion mathematically:

$$\vec{a} = \vec{0} \tag{14}$$

There are many circumstances where this would not be ideal, such as an elementwise multiplication of two vectors intended to cause a "blocking-operation" such as those seen in LSTMs. In *Sec. 4.1* an alternative to elementwise multiplication is shown which allows origin-centric inputs for the blocking-operation.

2.1.8 Continuous

A continuous function is our final greater criterion. With a discontinuous function, potential gaps are introduced into the manifold. There is no clear reason to do this and it just creates irregularities in the distribution of points in the manifold. This would make it more difficult for the network to further interpret manifolds, as datapoints representing similar things are artificially separated when they should have remained close. *Eqn. 15* describes this criterion mathematically:

$$(\forall \vec{\mu} \cap \forall \delta \cap \exists (\epsilon > 0)), \left(\left| \vec{F}(\vec{x}) - \vec{F}(\vec{x} + \epsilon \vec{\mu}) \right| < \delta \right) \tag{15}$$

Functions such as the step function violate many of the criteria, but particularly the discontinuity causes the uncontrolled loss of large amounts of information from the manifold, as several regions of the manifold are collapsed to singular points. This should be avoided as it is a pseudo-abstractive process since it decreases the local intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold despite

preserving the global intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold. In effect, this function can be considered to separate one manifold into many - with each having a much lower intrinsic dimensionality

2.2 Lesser Criteria

Lesser criteria are criteria which are probably not as important and empirically do not compromise the effectiveness of activation functions to as severe degree as the greater criteria. However, they should be considered if possible.

2.2.1 Bounded Functions

Bounded Functions are referring to the output space of an activation function being finite. Thus, as the magnitude of an input vector drawn from the centre of the input space goes to infinity, the image of the vector by the activation function reaches some finite limiting magnitude from the centre of the space.

From the origin-centricity postulate we can assume the network tries to distribute manifolds so that they occupy a range of directions about the origin. For non-spherically symmetric activation functions such as ReLU and Leaky-ReLU this means that the manifold is always likely to be distributed over a zone of non-linearity as the non-linearity is directional, hence fulfilling the non-linear criterion. However, the origin-centricity postulate does not state that the manifold also occupies all range of magnitudes from the centre of the space. Therefore, in the special circumstance of a localised non-linearity, a spherically symmetric function (where the non-linearity varies radially) may result in the manifold not being distributed over a non-linear zone. Hence, the manifold has 'escaped' the local non-linearity, resulting in an effective linear activation function - violating the non-linear criterion. This is shown in *Sec. 7.2* where a naive implementation of a criteria-meeting adaptation of the Leaky-ReLU function failed empirically due to the manifold existing in only one of two linear regions sharing a non-linear boundary. This was partially remedied by broadening the non-linear boundary so that the activation was smooth but the problem persisted as whole.

Additionally, excessively large activations (allowed by unbounded functions) can potentially compromise the functionality of a network due to overstimulation of neurons and 'drowning out' of other important activations. This would require a form of batch normalisation to rectify the issue - thus is another reason for the bounded function criterion. Further, bounded functions introduce extreme non-linearities since infinite space is compacted into finite space. This harsher non-linearity may be beneficial to the network as it requires less transformations to reshape the manifold in a useful way.

Eqn. 16 is an expression describing this criterion:

$$(\forall \vec{x} \cap (\exists \mu \in \mathbb{R}) \cap \exists \vec{u}), \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} \vec{F}(\epsilon \hat{x}) = \mu \hat{u} \quad (16)$$

3 Criteria Fulfilling Activation Functions

In this section several criteria-fulfilling functions are presented which are adaptations of commonly used activation functions such as Sigmoid, Tanh and various types of ReLU.

3.1 Application to Tensors

The application of elementwise functions is trivial for tensors of all shapes and sizes - likewise for the following functions when applied to a vector. However, it is not obvious how to apply the following functions to larger tensors such as those produced by convolutions. There are two ways of implementing these new functions: either depthwise or batchwise. Depthwise is described by separating the tensor into many vectors, applying the function to each of these vectors then restacking the vectors into the tensor. Batchwise is the preferable method which consists of taking each batch's data tensor and treating it as a vector - applying the function to the whole tensor at once. Reshaping of the tensor into a vector does not need to occur for batchwise applications, instead it can just be squared then summed over to obtain the magnitude squared. Therefore batchwise was used to test the functions since it is computationally more efficient. Alike performance should be observed between each application method.

3.2 Gees-Tanh Function

The "Gees-Tanh Function", shown in *Eqn. 17*, is an adaptation of the standard Tanh/Sigmoid activation function which meets all of the greater and lesser criteria. Improvements should be observed by replacing most general uses of standard Tanh and Sigmoid within neural networks. However, it does have altered bounds to the standard Sigmoid and Tanh function. Therefore, where bounds are important, such as the hyper-cubic $0 < \vec{x}_i < 1$ bound for Sigmoid acting as a blocking signal in an elementwise multiplication, Gees-Tanh should not be used as an alternative. However, *Sec. 4.1* describes an alternative formulation for these blocking-gates. When applied elementwise, Gees-Tanh is equivalent to Tanh.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \hat{x} \tanh |\vec{x}| \tag{17}$$

Where \vec{x} is the cartesian coordinates of the input data point. The function becomes undefined at $\vec{x} = \vec{0}$ so is defined as $\vec{0}$. Henceforth, the definition of $\hat{0}$ is $\hat{0} = \vec{0}$. Though all functions can be more formally described as a piecewise function as shown in *Eqn. 18*:

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \begin{cases} \hat{x} \tanh |\vec{x}| & : \vec{x} \neq \vec{0} \\ \vec{x} & : \vec{x} = \vec{0} \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

The gradient at zero is therefore defined by *Eqn. 19*.

$$\left. \frac{\partial \vec{F}(\vec{x}_i)}{\partial \vec{x}_j} \right|_{\vec{0}} = \left. \frac{\partial \vec{x}_i}{\partial \vec{x}_j} \right|_{\vec{0}} = \delta_{i,j} \quad (19)$$

An optional scaling parameter ($\alpha > 0$) can also be introduced as shown in Eqn. 20. However, this variant of the function is not tested in the results sections.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \hat{x} \tanh |\alpha \vec{x}| \quad (20)$$

Figure. 8 indicates how the standard Geebs-Tanh function conforms to all the criteria:

Figure 8: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Centre) shows the image of the input space through a Tanh mapping. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geebs-Tanh mapping. It can be observed that the typical Tanh does not fulfil the criteria whereas the modified-Tanh meets all the criteria. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/wybyi4a81o>.

3.3 Geebs-ReLU Function

The "Geebs-ReLU Function", shown in Eqn. 21, is an analogue of the Leaky-ReLU function. It meets all the greater criteria, but does not meet the bounded criteria by definition of a ReLU function. On a note of semantics: 'Rectifier' refers to the removal of a negative signal, which is not the case for Geebs-ReLU (nor is Geebs-ReLU linear, though it does tend to be linear as $|\vec{x}| \gg \beta$), however the term Rectified-Linear-Unit (ReLU) was kept due to its close association to the actual ReLU functions despite not technically being a ReLU function.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \left(\frac{\delta(1-\alpha)}{2} \left(\ln \cosh \left(\frac{|\vec{x}| - \beta}{\delta} \right) - \ln \cosh \left(\frac{\beta}{\delta} \right) \right) + \frac{1+\alpha}{2} |\vec{x}| \right) \hat{x} \quad (21)$$

Where ($0 \leq \alpha < 1$), ($0 < \beta$) and ($0 < \delta$) are parameters defining the leaky-gradient, offset at smoothing respectively. It applies a scaling given by α within a certain radius of the origin given by β . Although the scaling smoothly transitions from α to 1 around the boundary over a length defined by δ . Consequently, we get a function analogous to a typical Leaky-ReLU function except its scaling is applied within a certain radius of the origin instead of the

when the sign of a Cartesian coordinate component is negative. In addition it also differs slightly due to the gradient smoothly changing between linear regions instead of an abrupt change at the boundary. Geesbs-ReLU, like Leaky-ReLU, does not suffer from gradients tending to zero as the input radius tends to infinity, therefore will not suffer badly from vanishing gradients. Initially a non-smooth formulation equivalent to $\delta \rightarrow 0$ (and more similar to standard Leaky-ReLU) was used instead, but it was found empirically that the manifold suffered from the 'escaping non-linearity' problem discussed in *Sec. 2.2.1*. This intermediary function is discussed in *Sec. 7.2*.

From inspection *Eqn. 21* appears computationally intensive but many terms are constants so need to only be calculated once. By defining the constants shown in *Eqn. 22* and *Eqn. 23*:

$$\gamma^{\pm} = \frac{1 \pm \alpha}{2} \quad (22)$$

$$\tau = -\gamma^{-} \delta \ln \left(\cosh \left(\frac{\beta}{\delta} \right) \right) \quad (23)$$

Then many terms in *Eqn. 21* can be precalculated as constants. Resulting in function *Eqn. 21* simplifying to *Eqn. 24*:

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \left(\gamma^{-} \delta \ln \cosh \left(\frac{|\vec{x}| - \beta}{\delta} \right) + \tau + \gamma^{+} |\vec{x}| \right) \hat{x} \quad (24)$$

Finally, a $\ln \cosh(x)$ can be computationally expensive for $|x| \gg 0$. Moreover it can result in the number exceeding allocated memory when $|x| \gg 0$. This is because an intermediary value of $\cosh(x)$ must be stored and calculated before it can be put through the logarithm. Since $\ln(\cosh(x)) \approx \ln(0.5e^{|x|}) = |x| - \ln 2$ for $|x| \gg 0$ then $\ln \cosh(x)$ can be well approximated by the piecewise function shown in *Eqn. 25*.

$$\ln(\cosh(x)) \approx G(x) = \begin{cases} \ln(\cosh(x)) & : |x| \leq \epsilon \\ |x| - \ln 2 & : |x| > \epsilon \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

It was found that $\epsilon \approx 4$ produced a good approximation to a high degree of accuracy. Therefore, the final Geesbs-ReLU activation function is given by *Eqn. 26*:

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \left(G \left(\frac{|\vec{x}| - \beta}{\delta} \right) \delta \gamma^{-} + \tau + \gamma^{+} |\vec{x}| \right) \hat{x} \quad (26)$$

Careful tuning of parameters α , β and δ may be required to ensure that the manifold does not 'escape' the non-linearity effects. Although a special form of batch-normalisation[8], briefly discussed at the end of *Sec. 1.2*, can be used so that the parameters can remain constant for all network types - therefore they only need to be optimised once. This use of Geesbs-ReLU with normalisation is discussed in *Sec. 5.2*. Figure 9 shows the function compared with a Leaky-ReLU function.

Figure 9: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Centre) shows the image of the input space through a Leaky-ReLU mapping. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geebs-ReLU mapping. Values $\alpha = 0.1$, $\beta = 2$ and $\delta = 1$ were arbitrarily chosen. It can be seen that the non-linearity appears less 'extreme' for Geebs-ReLU, this is likely not an advantage but may also be addressed by normalisation. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/wybyi4a81o>.

Interestingly, if the values $\alpha = 0.00$, $\beta \approx 0.98$ and $\delta \approx -0.70$ are used in Geebs-ReLU, a function emerges which is almost identical to Geebs-Tanh. Perhaps Geebs-ReLU could then be considered a generalisation of Geebs-Tanh. The similarity can be seen more clearly with their respective derivatives: where Geebs-Tanh produces $1 - \tanh^2(x)$ like term, whilst Geebs-ReLU produces a $1 - \tanh|x|$ like term.

3.4 Box-Cut-Off Function and Geebs-Sigmoid Function

There are some unique use cases in which the modified functions are not immediately applicable due to their spherically-bounded or unbounded output space. As mentioned in *Sec. 2.1.5*, some networks require a hyper-cubic bounding to the activation function's output space. An example of this is the aforementioned 'blocking-gates' where a hyper-cubic output space is required which is bounded between zero (blocked) and one (passed) for each component in a neuron-basis. This is incompatible with the spherical symmetry criterion, but since this is a specific use case the generalised criteria do not apply. Alternatively, the blocking gate consisting of an elementwise multiplication can be instead replaced with the formulation described in *Sec. 4.1* which accepts inputs which do not have to be hyper-cubically bound - this is the preferable solution to be more in alignment with the criteria.

Equation 27 describes a function which projects the input space into a hyper-cubic space bounded between -1 and 1 for all neuron-basis components. A typical box-cut-off (minimum-maximum) function cannot be used here as demonstrated in *Fig. 7*. In effect *Eqn. 27* preserves the space between $-1 < \vec{x}_i < 1$ whilst radially projecting all space outside this region onto a hyper-cubic shell.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \min\left(\frac{1}{\max(|\vec{x}_1|, |\vec{x}_2|, \dots, |\vec{x}_i|)}, 1\right) \times \vec{x} \quad (27)$$

If an analogue of the Sigmoid function used in long-short-term-memory networks [9] (LSTMs) is required then a Geebs-Tanh ($\vec{T}(\vec{x})$) function coupled with

the box-cutoff function ($\vec{B}(\vec{x})$) can be used as a replacement as shown in *Eqn. 28*. This has the correct hyper-cubic bounds of $0 < \vec{x}_i < 1$.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\vec{B}\left(\sqrt{2}\vec{T}(\vec{x})\right) + \vec{1}}{2} \quad (28)$$

Where the $\sqrt{2}$ factor is the minimum scaling of Geesbs-Tanh required to ensure the required bounds for the function are met, however we propose the multiplicative factor should be 2 to ensure the identity gradient criterion is satisfied. Note that this multiplicative factor is not a scaling of the input such as: $\vec{T}(2\vec{x})$ as described in *Sec. 2.1.6*. The final formulation of Geesbs-Sigmoid is described in *Eqn. 29*.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\vec{B}\left(2\vec{T}(\vec{x})\right) + \vec{1}}{2} \quad (29)$$

Eqn. 28 is analogous to Sigmoid, meeting more criteria. However, it does not satisfy the spherical-symmetric criterion after a certain magnitude nor the centre-at-the-origin criterion. For any function which by definition must violate some criteria, efforts should be made to ensure as many criteria as possible are met. In addition, specific purpose activation functions are always preferable but it is not always feasible to design a new activation function for every scenario. Figure 10 shows standard Sigmoid and *Eqn. 28* - it can be observed that the latter fulfills more criteria.

Figure 10: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Centre) shows the image of the input space through a Sigmoid mapping. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geesbs-Sigmoid mapping. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/wybyi4a81o>.

With these three activation functions, almost all general use cases of activation functions now have alternative formulations which meet more criteria.

4 Criteria Fulfilling Operations

Though the criteria are specifically designed for application to activation functions, some neural network operations may also benefit from criteria inspired

changes. The following functions are dependent on multiple vectors - instead of one in the case of activation functions. Hence, the criteria are not well defined in these cases. Most neural network operations are already optimised, from the perspective of the above criteria, such as elementwise-addition and matrix multiplication as an example. Both these functions ensure indistinguishable neurons from within activation-space. Yet, others such as elementwise multiplication, minimum and maximum functions can be changed to be more inline with the criteria. Since these are not the main subject of this paper they remain a theoretical idea which are included as the reader may find them useful.

4.1 Gees-Multiplication for Blocking Gates

As mentioned, elementwise multiplication is often used to create a blocking gate within the network. This is done by multiplication of a signal vector (\vec{s}) with a blocking vector ($0 \leq \vec{b}_i \leq 1$), causing the reduction of magnitude for some components in the signal vector. This is described in *Eqn. 30*. However, this process is neuron-basis aligned so does not meet the spherical-symmetry criterion and the blocking signal does not meet the origin-at-centre criterion. An alternative formulation is described in *Eqn. 31*, where the component scaling is not basis aligned and is instead acting in the direction of the blocking vector. In effect, only the component of the vectors in the direction of the blocking vectors is scaled. The scaling factor is equal to the magnitude of the blocking vector.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{s}, \vec{b}) = \vec{s} \odot \vec{b} \tag{30}$$

However, this modified formulation, shown in *Eqn. 31*, is not ideal as it can only reduce the intrinsic dimensionality by one dimension at most at a time, whereas standard elementwise-multiplication can reduce the manifold’s intrinsic dimensionality by any amount. To make a spherically symmetric operation which can reduce the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold by any amount would require $2N - 1$ degrees of freedom for an N dimensional manifold as opposed to the N degrees of freedom for standard elementwise and gees multiplication. This spherically-symmetric multi-directional blocking operation could be achieved by use of a rotation matrix and its inverse applied: $\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\vec{b} \odot (\mathbf{R}\vec{x}))$.

A potentially important feature of elementwise-multiplication is the commutativity of the input vectors. This can mean the roles of a blocking vector and signal vector can reverse more easily. This could be a useful mechanism where two networks act together: one dedicated to producing information and one designed to regulate and control that information. It enables a network ordinarily performing a regulating task to, by happenstance, begin to learn how to transmit information too. In the long term the lack of commutativity may be more detrimental than any short term benefits it may bring.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{s}, \vec{b}) = \vec{s} + \left(\left(\frac{|\vec{b}|}{|\vec{s}|} - 1 \right) \vec{s} \cdot \hat{b} \right) \hat{b} \tag{31}$$

The magnitude of \vec{b} , given by $|\vec{b}|$, is proportional to the scaling factor on \vec{s} , so if Eqn. 31 is to be used as a blocking-gate then \vec{b} needs to have a maximum magnitude of one: $0 \leq |\vec{b}| \leq 1$. This can be achieved by defining $\vec{b} = T(\vec{c})$, where $T(\vec{x})$ is the Geesbs-Tanh function and \vec{c} the initially unbounded blocking-vector. In Fig. 11 both standard elementwise-multiplication and Geesbs-multiplication are shown. It can be seen that elementwise-multiplication scales in the direction of the neuron-basis-vectors whereas Geesbs-multiplication scales in the direction of the blocking-vector only.

Figure 11: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with a standard-normally-distributed point cloud in purple (these represent the signal-vectors in a manifold). The orange line is the blocking vector's direction and magnitude given by $\vec{b} = T(\vec{c})$. (Centre) shows the resulting point-cloud from an elementwise multiplication between the initial input point cloud and blocking vector. (Right) shows the resulting point-cloud from an Geesbs-multiplication between the initial input point cloud and blocking vector. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/morbsp9v1n>.

4.2 Pivotal Min and Max Function

In Sec. 3.4 a box-cutoff function was defined such that more criteria were met when creating a Sigmoid-like function. In this section the more general minimum and maximum functions are redefined too to be inline with the criteria. Standard minimum and maximum functions are usually applied elementwise to tensors resulting in a direction-dependent cutoff. Instead, "Geesbs-Min" and "Geesbs-Max" utilise an arbitrary hyperplane, defined by its normal vector, at which to cut off lines past the hyperplane and before it respectively. The distance and direction, from the origin, of the hyperplane are defined by a single input vector. Equations 32 and 33 express the Geesbs-Min and Geesbs-Max functions respectively.

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}, \vec{n}) = \min \left(\text{sign}(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n}), \left| \frac{\vec{n} \cdot \vec{n}}{\vec{n} \cdot \vec{x}} \right| \right) \text{sign}(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n}) \vec{x} \quad (32)$$

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}, \vec{n}) = \max \left(\text{sign}(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n}), \left| \frac{\vec{n} \cdot \vec{n}}{\vec{n} \cdot \vec{x}} \right| \right) \text{sign}(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n}) \vec{x} \quad (33)$$

Where \vec{n} is the normal vector defining the hyperplane, \hat{n} defines the direction of the hyperplane and $|\vec{n}|$ defines the distance of the hyperplane from the origin.

In addition, Geesbs-Min and Geesbs-Max functions are also defined by $\vec{F}(\vec{0}, \vec{n}) = \vec{0}$ and $\vec{F}(\vec{x}, \vec{0}) = \vec{x}$.

With the Geesbs-Max function a unique issue arises with the projection criterion. Vectors are projected forward onto the plane resulting in opposite directions, as measured from the origin, mapping onto the same point on the hyperplane. As discussed in *Sec. 1.2*, the origin-centricity postulate infers that two properties considered opposite in the manifold are represented as opposite directions in activation space. Thus, potentially contradictory properties are mapped to the same point making them incorrectly appear similar. The potential implications of this must be considered before implementation of Geesbs-max into an arbitrary network. Both Geesbs-Min and Geesbs-Max are displayed in *Fig. 12*.

Figure 12: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. The purple dot indicates the normal vector which defines the hyperplane and the hyperplane is displayed in faint grey. (Centre-Left) shows the image of the input space through a Standard-Max mapping, the cutoff is observed to be directional and lines through the origin trace along the boundary as discussed in *Sec. 2.1.5*. (Centre-Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geesbs-Min mapping where points passed the plane are cutoff and projected back onto the plane (as seen by the lack of trailing lines for any line passing through the origin such as the green lines). (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geesbs-Max mapping where points before the plane are projected forward onto the plane. Interactive demonstration available at: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/morbsp9v1n>.

5 Results And Analysis

5.1 Geesbs-Tanh

Geesbs-Tanh is an analogue of the Sigmoid and Tanh activation functions. Therefore, the performances of Sigmoid, Tanh and Geesbs-Tanh are to be compared for several different datasets, including MNIST and CIFAR[13]. Several different fully-connected classification networks are used to test these activation functions. For every permutation of activation function, dataset and network architecture, identical tests are repeated thirty times in order to obtain mean and standard-deviations for the performance metrics.

Every test used the Adam-Optimiser[10] on a mean-squared-error cost, a batch-size of 5000 random training samples and the network was trained for 10000 epochs. Metrics are obtained using an unseen testing batch consisting of 5000 samples. We define one epoch as the presentation of one mini-batch to the network. Due to lack of computational resources, all results do under-perform

the state-of-the-art classification accuracies seen in other papers - therefore the relative performance between our tests will be compared rather than comparing against results in the literature.

To quantify the success of the activation functions, two ensemble metrics were defined: *maximum accuracy improvement rate* (MAIR) and *learning latency*. Maximum accuracy improvement rate describes the maximum change in the average accuracy per epoch. The higher the MAIR, the better the activation function is considered to perform. It gives an indication how long a given network takes to train. Learning latency describes the number of training epochs taken before a statistically non-random accuracy is observed for the network. This is considered to be when $10\% \leq \mu_t - 3\sigma_t$, where μ_t is the mean accuracy across the ten repeats at time step t , likewise σ_t is the standard deviation on accuracy across the same ten repeats at time step t . 10% is used as the threshold accuracy as this is the average accuracy achieved when the MNIST and CIFAR datasets are classified randomly. The lower the latency, the faster the network begins performing to a better than random chance. This gives an indication of how long the network takes to train. Thus, low-latency is a measure of the success of the activation function. All accuracy measurements are obtained from the network’s performance on the test dataset.

Stagnation-accuracy is also a useful metric. Stagnation-accuracy is defined as the accuracy reached as the accuracy change per epoch tends to zero. This is performed on each of the thirty repeats, then the average and standard-deviation is found. If a network reaches a higher stagnation accuracy than another network it is considered to have performed better. It has been noticed in previous personal experiments that sigmoid tends to intermittently stagnate then have sudden jumps in accuracy, potentially making its true stagnation very difficult to judge. Therefore stagnation-accuracy was approximated to be the accuracy achieved after 10000 epochs (unless a dip in accuracy occurred at which point the initial stagnated maximum accuracy is chosen). Whether this value is representative of the true stagnation-accuracy will be discussed as the network does not necessarily experience learning stagnation up to 10000 epochs.

The ensemble metrics were then calculated across 10 repetitions of each activation function and network architecture. However, to ensure mean and standard deviation of the ensemble metrics could be determined, three independent measurements of ensemble metrics were calculated resulting in of total 30 repeats for each activation function on each network. These were then arbitrarily grouped into three groups of ten repeats to calculate the ensemble metrics. The decision to use ensemble metrics was taken primarily so learning-latency could be measured, but in addition MAIR may be affected by accuracies momentarily spiking then collapsing rather than the general slope of increasing accuracy which was intended to be measured - this error is reduced by using an ensemble metric.

5.1.1 MNIST: Fully-Connected Networks

The criterion described in *Sec. 2.1.6* was intended to reduce the vanishing and exploding gradient problems and these problems typically arise in deep neural networks. Therefore, the modified activation functions are expected to perform better in deep neural networks as opposed to 'shallow networks'. Where the depth refers to the number of layers. For this reason a range of fully-connected neural networks were chosen such that the number of layers varied from shallow to unnecessarily deep. Many of the below network structures are considered excessive to solving the MNIST problem, however it will give an indication of how well the Gees-Tanh performs on deeper neural networks. It is expected that a marked improvement should be observed for Gees-Tanh in the deeper networks. The following network architectures were tested:

Network Structure (Neurons per Layer)	Number Of Layers
[784, 10]	2 Layers
[784, 500, 10]	3 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 10]	4 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 10]	5 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	6 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	7 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	8 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	9 Layers
[784, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	10 Layers

The specified activation function is applied after every layer, including the final layer (no softmax was used). It is expected that the MAIR metric will increase to a maximum, reaching the maximum when the network has just sufficient depth to 'solve' the MNIST dataset. Conversely, shallower networks are expected to have a lower MAIR score due to having insufficient size to effectively classify MNIST. Further, it is expected that the MAIR score will begin to decrease after reaching this maximum. This is because as the number of network layers are increased it will less efficiently train due to an excessive quantity of redundant neurons. Moreover, there is an increased likelihood of vanishing, exploding and diluting gradients with larger networks. [Figure 13](#) displays a plot of the MAIR measured for each activation function and network architectures. The original data can be found in *Tab. 2, Sec. 8.1*.

Figure 13: Displays the MAIR metric for Geebs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green). It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh has the highest MAIR across all network architectures.

All activation functions began with a similar MAIR score on the shallowest network, although it can be seen that Geebs-Tanh is the most successful activation function on the MAIR metric for all fully-connected network architectures tested afterwards. In addition, Geebs-Tanh outperforms Sigmoid and Tanh by many standard deviations. Sigmoid has a better score than Tanh for deeper networks, though they perform similarly on shallower networks. The predicted trend of reaching a maximum MAIR was observed for Tanh, however, was not observed in Geebs-Tanh and Sigmoid which continue to increase even after the network is of apparent sufficient depth to 'solve' MNIST. For the range of depths tested, Geebs-Tanh shows an apparent linear increase in MAIR score with increasing number of network layers. It is possible that Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh do reach a maximum at some larger network depth, however more data would need to be collected to confirm this. This linear increase was unexpected for Geebs-Tanh; it gives an indication that the larger the network, the faster it trains. This result is somewhat counter-intuitive for a simple dataset such as MNIST. It would be expected that a deeper network has greater capacity to learn more complex representations thus increasing stagnation accuracy. However, this does not explain the increased learning rate.

If accuracy also shows an increase at greater depth after 10000, it will indicate that this increased learning rate is sustained - this will be indicated by stagnation accuracy. Figure 14 displays the stagnation-accuracy which is tabulated in *Tab. 3, Sec. 8.1*.

Figure 14: Displays the stagnation accuracy for Geebs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green). It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh has a higher stagnation-accuracy across all network architectures.

It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh reaches, on average, the highest stagnation accuracy across all network depths. Sigmoid performs similarly to Geebs-Tanh for shallower networks before it begins to decrease at a greater number of layers, whilst Geebs-Tanh begins to increase. The error on Sigmoid is much larger than Geebs-Tanh, showing it is less consistent but may outperform Geebs-Tanh occasionally. Tanh under-performs Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh by a large margin, this is in agreement with literature. Sigmoid reaches a maximum before decreasing, this is thought to be caused by the same reason as discussed for the MAIR metric. Though it will be seen in *Fig. 16* that Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh do not actually reach stagnation at these greater depths, so Sigmoid’s reduction in accuracy after 10000 epochs may instead be due to a reduction in average learning rate. It can be seen in *Fig. 14* that the stagnation accuracy for Geebs-Tanh begins to increase again at greater depths. This is partially due a deeper network being able to learn more complex representations but it can be seen in *Fig. 16* that Geebs-Tanh actually begins to accelerate in learning rate after reaching an initial stagnation point. This indicates that the stagnation accuracy in *Fig. 14* is an underestimate of its true value and that it is likely to increase further with greater depth and training time.

The results for Geebs-Tanh corroborate the findings in *Fig. 13* that the deeper the network; the faster learning occurs. As stated, this property of Geebs-Tanh was unexpected and is potentially extremely beneficial. Although the number of epochs are not immediately proportional to computation time, due to the increasing computational cost of running a deeper neural network, if the computer is sufficiently parallelised then epochs become more proportional to computation time. Thus, this feature of Geebs-Tanh may perhaps make very deep-networks viable to train in a reasonable time using a highly parallelised

computer - enabling the design and training of more complicated networks. This may make it feasible to train on datasets which were previously inaccessible due to long training (and thus computation) time required.

Finally, the logged-latency of the activation functions is displayed in *Fig. 15*, the numerical results are displayed in *Tab. 4* in *Sec. 8.1*.

Figure 15: Displays the logged-latency for Geebs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green). It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh’s latency goes to one (the shortest latency possible) with deeper network architecture.

The trend in logged-latency for Tanh is not clear, though Sigmoid shows an increase with increasing network depth, whilst Geebs-Tanh shows a decrease. This separation between Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh at greater depths is statistically significant with many standard deviations between their respective values. Thus, Geebs-Tanh is also considered the best performing activation function on the latency metric. In addition, Geebs-Tanh’s latency tends to one with greater number of network layers, this means that it reaches non-random performance in just one epoch - this is the minimum value this metric can take. This is fairly remarkable as it has only been trained on one batch of just 5000 samples, but has learned to generalise to achieve significant accuracy on an unseen test-set.

Fig. 15 again indicates that the deeper the network; the faster it learns when using Geebs-Tanh. Whilst the existing activation functions appear to reduce in learning speed with the increase of network size. This potentially makes Geebs-Tanh favourable in many applications, making very deep networks viable. It is unclear the exact mechanism of how Geebs-Tanh achieves this besides the general aims of the criteria - it is thought to be a result of Geebs-Tanh causing cost-valley steepening. This will be discussed shortly.

Figure 16 displays an excerpt of the results for networks of layers 2, 8 and 10. Other results can be found in *Sec. 8.1* in figures 37 through 39.

Figure 16: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 2 (Left), 8 (Center), 10 (Right)) trained on MNIST using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geesbs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the mean accuracies of Geesbs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively at each epoch across 30 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 10 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

These graphics agree with the analysis of the metrics. However, it does indicate that neither Sigmoid or Geesbs-Tanh reached final stagnation at any network depth - more results need to be gathered to find their true stagnation accuracies. It is also apparent that the accuracy curve is initially much steeper for deeper networks using Geesbs-Tanh whereas becomes increasingly gradual for Sigmoid and Tanh. It can also be seen that on average Geesbs-Tanh outperforms Sigmoid and Tanh on accuracy at any epoch, though the error for Sigmoid is much larger suggesting that Sigmoid can infrequently outperform Geesbs-Tanh. Although this becomes less likely with increasing network depths. The outliers resulting in Sigmoid’s large standard deviation were also found to be always under-performance, suggesting the large standard deviation observed is misleading. There was no run where Sigmoid out-performed any repeat Geesbs-Tanh in the 7, 8, 9 or 10 layer networks. The standard deviation on Geesbs-Tanh is much smaller than that for Sigmoid. This suggests Geesbs-Tanh is more consistent than Sigmoid even when the initialisation is different. We propose this is due to the aforementioned cost-valley steepening. In effect, the cost-valleys for Geesbs-Tanh are generally translationally invariant with sparse minima - such that (as usual) the network is unlikely to be initialised on a minima. This general translational invariance, means the cost-valley appears roughly similar for the majority of random-normal initialisations of the network resulting in the network learning more consistently when using Geesbs-Tanh. This produces very similar learning curves as follow similar trajectories down different cost-valley.

Another feature, unique to the Geesbs-Tanh learning curves, is the acceleration in learning after an initial stagnation period. This is found to be more likely with deeper networks. It can be clearly seen, in *Fig. 16*, for both the 8 and 10 layer network tests. This was again unexpected and potentially very advantageous as results in better performing networks. We propose the acceleration is due to the effective momentum factor in the Adam’s optimiser used to train the networks. This is likely to be a result of the cost-valley steepening again. One can think of Sigmoid’s cost-valleys as being bumpy hills and valleys which the network traverses down steadily in various directions, whereas the Geesbs-Tanh cost-valleys are more analogous to cliffs and basins. Thus, an ini-

tial stagnation occurs for Geebs-Tanh after falling from the 'cliff' into the basin, but then momentum increases again such that it traverses the basin faster until reaching the minima. Due to the bumps in Sigmoid's cost valleys, it is suspected that the direction of steepest descent varies often, resulting in a less effective momentum, whereas the Geebs-Tanh valleys are more direct.

In *Fig. 17*, it shows the average cross section for a cost-valley under Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh. These are average cross-sections which were obtained by training 10, 12-layer fully-connected networks. However, these cross-sections give no indication of the changing direction of steepest descent, theorised to be advantageous to Geebs-Tanh. In this test, the Adadelata Optimiser[12] was used as an optimiser rather than the Adam Optimiser used previously - this was so that the momentum term did not distort the cost-surface profile. Learning rate was also kept constant at $\eta = 0.01$. No momentum ensures that the cost-surface profile obtained is representative of the true surface, such that consistent sized 'steps' are made by the network down the slope. Then the cost at each epoch was measured, for each repeat, and averaged to get an approximate profile of the cost-surface. These cost profiles were also normalised so the average final cost reached is zero and the initial average cost is one, this was so that the cost profiles could be compared. Adadelata also tends to take the path with the largest decrease in cost at each step, thus, these profiles are the steepest contour of the cost surface.

Figure 17: Displays the cost for Geebs-Tanh (Left) and Sigmoid (Right) on a 12-layer network using the adadelata optimiser across 10 repeats each. The mean cost is displayed in thick opaque line, whilst the region enclosing the mean plus and minus one standard deviation is shaded. Individual cost runs are shown in faint coloured lines.

Although, the average cost surface for Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh is similar, it can be seen that the individual cost profiles for Sigmoid have more variation. This agrees with the 'bumpy hills' expected for Sigmoid, which likely also indicate direction changes for the steepest descent. The repeats for Geebs-Tanh have less variation indicating the translational invariance concept proposed for Geebs-Tanh. The cliff and basin notion would require more data to validate, but it appears Geebs-Tanh has one large basin as opposed to how Sigmoid's costs has many flat regions interspersed with steep descents.

The results for Gees-Tanh undermine the established understanding of the vanishing gradient problem. The vanishing gradient problem is often attributed to the saturation of activation functions such as Tanh, Sigmoid and Arctan - where the gradient tends to zero at large magnitudes. Gees-Tanh's gradients also tend to zero, but it does not appear to suffer from the vanishing gradient problem, instead the opposite phenomena occurs where performance improves with network depth as can be seen in *Fig. 13*, *Fig. 14* and *Fig. 15*. This casts doubt on whether the cause is specifically the saturation behaviour of the bounded functions, instead it may be another undetermined aspect of their derivatives causing this issue.

5.1.2 CIFAR: Fully-Connected Networks

The same tests performed on MNIST will be repeated for a similar network trained on CIFAR. A range of network depths were again tested to if the performance of the functions is affected by network size. This is to ensure results are generally valid across different datasets. The results will not be discussed as in depth as MNIST, since many discussed concepts are equally applicable to CIFAR. The following networks structures were tested in the exact same procedure as for MNIST.

Network Structure (Neurons per Layer)	Number Of Layers
[3072, 10]	2 Layers
[3072, 500, 10]	3 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 10]	4 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 10]	5 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	6 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	7 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	8 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	9 Layers
[3072, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 500, 10]	10 Layers

The results for the MAIR metric are displayed in *Fig. 18* and the numerical results can be found in *Tab. 5* in *Sec. 8.2*.

Figure 18: Displays the MAIR metric for Geesbs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green), across various depth networks trained on the CIFAR dataset.

It can be seen that standard-Tanh reaches a maximum at 6 network layers, but reduces either side of this optimum depth. This was predicted in the discussion in *Sec. 5.1.1*. However, across the data collected, Geesbs-Tanh and Sigmoid showed a steady increase in MAIR with deeper networks. No maximum was observed across the data collected. Geesbs-Tanh outperformed Sigmoid across all networks tested, however, standard-Tanh outperformed Geesbs-Tanh around its maximum value. This indicates it had a faster training time, but this was not sustained as the final stagnation accuracy is found to be lower for standard-Tanh than for Geesbs-Tanh as shown in *Fig. 19*. The MAIR results for CIFAR were found to be in agreement overall with the findings for MNIST. Though there was not as large of a separation between the performance of the different functions, this is likely due to CIFAR being considered a more challenging dataset.

Below, *Fig. 19* shows the results for the stagnation accuracies of the functions. The numerical results can be found in *Tab. 6* in *Sec. 8.2*.

Figure 19: Displays the stagnation accuracy for Geesbs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green), across various depth networks trained on the CIFAR dataset.

These results are comparable to those found for MNIST, it can be seen that Geesbs-Tanh outperforms the other functions across all networks tested. Sigmoid and Geesbs-Tanh exhibit similar performance for shallower networks, but Sigmoids performance begins to decrease, whilst Geesbs-Tanh increase for deeper networks. This supports the conclusions made for Geesbs-Tanh in *Sec. 5.1.1*. It was found that neither Sigmoid or Geesbs-Tanh reached stagnation in their performance, indicating further improvements could be attained with more training time. *Fig. 20*, shows an excerpt of the data found in *Sec. 8.2* showing that larger networks, utilising Sigmoid and Geesbs-Tanh, did not reach learning stagnation after 10000 epochs.

Figure 20: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 2 (Left), 8 (Center), 10 (Right) trained on MNIST using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geesbs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the mean accuracies of Geesbs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively at each epoch across 30 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 10 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Figure 21 displays the logged-latencies across the various networks, the numerical results can be found in *Tab. 7* in *Sec. 8.2*.

Figure 21: Displays the logged-latencies metric for Geebs-Tanh (blue), Sigmoid (red) and Tanh (green), across various depth networks trained on the CIFAR dataset.

The logged-latencies show a clear trend for Geebs-Tanh of decreasing as the number of network layers increases. The trend was less clear for Sigmoid and Tanh but appeared to increase at greater number of network layers. Sigmoid and Tanh reached the maximum detectable value of latency = 9999 as the networks were made larger.

Overall, the CIFAR tests corroborated the findings in *Sec. 5.1.1* on MNIST, showing Geebs-Tanh performed far better than Sigmoid and Tanh. Furthermore, the networks utilising Geebs-Tanh seem to learn faster and achieve better overall accuracy as the network size increased. The latter phenomena may be expected due to larger networks being able to learn more complex representations but the former phenomena was not anticipated and its implications may be very advantageous for very-deep neural networks.

5.2 Geebs-ReLU

The Geebs-ReLU function is tested on a convolutional network with a varying number of layers. The MNIST training data is collated into 500-sample randomised mini-batches and the network was trained for 10000 epochs. The Adam optimiser was chosen to minimise a mean-squared error cost. The metrics discussed in *Sec. 5.1* were calculated using an unseen testing batch. Every permutation of activation function and depth of network was tested 30 times as before. The network architecture is described below:

Network Structure

(Layer Descriptions)

Layer 1: Convolution, Filter=[4, 4, 1, 16], Stride=[1, 1]

*Layer 2: Convolution, Filter=[4, 4, 16, 16], Stride=[1, 1]

Layer 3: Convolution, Filter=[4, 4, 16, 32], Stride=[2, 2]
 Layer 4: Convolution, Filter=[4, 4, 32, 48], Stride=[1, 1]
 Layer 5: Convolution, Filter=[4, 4, 48, 64], Stride=[2, 2]
 Layer 6: Convolution, Filter=[3, 3, 64, 96], Stride=[1, 1]
 Layer 7: Convolution, Filter=[7, 7, 96, 128], Stride=[7, 7]
 Layer 8: Fully Connected, Neuron per Layer=[128, 256, 256, 128, 64, 10]

No pooling layers were utilised nor batch-norm. The operation for layer 2 was repeated n times to produce the different depth networks. This exact architecture was not cherry-picked and it would be beneficial to test Geesbs-ReLU across a greater range of network architectures though this was out-of-scope for this paper. The Geesbs-ReLU parameters were chosen to be $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 4.25$ and $\delta = 4.25$ - which were the average optimum values found by a tree-search performed on various network architectures. The specified activation function was applied on layers 1 through 7, with layer 8 instead utilising a sigmoid activation function with no softmax on the final layer.

The MAIR metric is displayed in *Fig. 22* and tabulated in *Tab. 8* in *Sec. 8.3*.

Figure 22: Displays the MAIR metric for Geesbs-Tanh (red), Geesbs-ReLU (blue), Leaky-ReLU (green) and ReLU (yellow), across various depth networks trained on the MNIST dataset. It can be seen that Geesbs-Tanh has a higher MAIR across all network architectures.

It can be seen that Leaky-ReLU, ReLU and Geesbs-ReLU share similar performance on the MAIR metric, with standard ReLU being slightly higher across all depths of networks. Geesbs-Tanh shows significantly higher performance across all networks tested and also shows a trend of increasing performance in deeper networks. This further validates the findings in *Sec. 5.1.1* and *Sec. 5.1.2*, showing the trend of increasing performance was not limited to fully-connected

networks only. Although Geebs-Tanh also shows higher variation in the metric. From these results it would be recommended that Geebs-Tanh be used in place of the ReLU variants on convolutional architectures, despite Geebs-ReLU being specifically designed for this architecture. Ideally further results would be required to support this recommendation. In *Fig. 23* the results for stagnation accuracy are displayed, the numerical values can be found in *Tab. 9* in *Sec. 8.3*.

Figure 23: Displays the stagnation accuracies for Geebs-Tanh (red), Geebs-ReLU (blue), Leaky-ReLU (green) and ReLU (yellow), across various depth networks trained on the MNIST dataset. It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh has a higher stagnation-accuracy across all network architectures.

The stagnation accuracies of Leaky-ReLU and Geebs-ReLU are similar, showing roughly equal performance on the metric with a slight decreasing trend at greater network depths. ReLU underperformed both these activation functions by a significant amount and shows a stronger decrease in performance at greater network depths. This is likely due to the 'dying ReLU problem' where the gradient of the functions falls to zero for negative inputs, thus preventing further learning. Again Geebs-Tanh provides the highest values for stagnation accuracy across all networks tested. The variation of Geebs-Tanh is also much smaller than the other functions indicating its consistency. Geebs-Tanh also shows a slight increasing trend in stagnation accuracy as the network depth is increased. Again, this may allow very large networks to become viable when using Geebs-Tanh. All functions were found to stagnate across the 10000 epochs.

Finally the logged learning latency is shown in *Fig. 24*, the numerical values can be found in *Tab. 10* in *Sec. 8.3*.

Figure 24: Displays the logged learning latency for Geebs-Tanh (red), Geebs-ReLU (blue), Leaky-ReLU (green) and ReLU (yellow), across various depth networks trained on the MNIST dataset.

The variation across all activation functions was high, resulting in no significant difference between the functions. All functions show an initial increase in latency with increasing depth, followed by a downward trend. Geebs-ReLU does appear to have the lowest latency across many of the networks tested although this is not statistically significant.

Overall, on these metrics, Geebs-ReLU performed very similarly to the popular Leaky-ReLU activation function and slightly better on the learning latency metric. Both Geebs-ReLU and Leaky-ReLU significantly outperformed standard ReLU. Geebs-ReLU is more computationally intensive than Leaky-ReLU, so on these preliminary results Leaky-ReLU would be recommended out of the two. However, further testing across more network architectures and different metrics would need to be performed to establish which function is most beneficial universally. Geebs-Tanh was included in the results to see whether it was also useful in convolutional architectures, surprisingly it outperformed all the ReLU variants tested by a significant margin. Therefore, it would be recommended to use Geebs-Tanh in convolutional architectures from these results. This was success was unexpected and Geebs-Tanh shows signs of increasing performance with deeper architectures potentially increasing the viability of very large neural networks. Perhaps another variation of a Geebs-ReLU-like function could be designed to meet more criteria and this may yield more successful results. In addition, if hyper parameters were optimised specifically for this architecture an increased performance may have been observed. Allowing the network to optimise these parameters during backpropagation may also yield more successful results.

5.3 Geebs-Sigmoid

5.3.1 MNIST: Fully-Connected Networks

Geebs-Sigmoid was first tested under identical conditions to the test described in *Sec. 5.1.1*. The numerical values for all the metrics are located in *Sec. 8.1*. Figure 25 shows the results for MAIR metric.

Figure 25: Displays the MAIR metric for Geebs-Tanh (red), Geebs-Sigmoid (blue), Sigmoid (green) and Tanh (yellow).

In shallow networks Geebs-Sigmoid has the highest MAIR value by a significant margin, out-performing standard Sigmoid, however this quickly falls to a value comparable to standard Sigmoid in deeper networks. Geebs-Sigmoid reaches a peak at a network depth of four fully connected layers. Therefore, Geebs-Sigmoid is the most successful activation function in terms of the MAIR metric in shallow networks, but Geebs-Tanh surpasses Geebs-Sigmoid as the network is made larger. This indicates that Geebs-Sigmoid should only be used on a few successive network layers. This is acceptable in terms of its design purpose which was a blocking signal for an elementwise multiplication. In this scenario the Geebs-Sigmoid function can be used in the final layer of the network providing the blocking signal. This setup will be tested in *Sec. 5.3.2*.

In *Fig. 26* the stagnation accuracies for different activation functions are shown:

Figure 26: Displays the stagnation accuracy for Geebs-Tanh (red), Geebs-Sigmoid (blue), Sigmoid (green) and Tanh (yellow). It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh has a higher stagnation-accuracy across all network architectures.

For shallower networks Sigmoid, Geebs-Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh show comparable performance, however Geebs-Sigmoid drops at the fifth layer network - in agreement with the MAIR results. At larger networks the Geebs-Sigmoid function causes the network to achieve only 10% accuracy which is equivalent to guessing randomly. Overall this further indicates that Geebs-Sigmoid should only be applied on a few subsequent network layers to achieve good performance.

Finally, the logged-latency of the activation functions is displayed in *Fig. 27*:

Figure 27: Displays the logged-latency for Geebs-Tanh (red), Geebs-Sigmoid (blue), Sigmoid (green) and Tanh (yellow). It can be seen that Geebs-Tanh’s latency goes to one (the shortest latency possible) with deeper network architecture.

Geebs-Sigmoid’s latency shows little trend across the networks tested and it is found to under-perform standard Sigmoid on latency across shallower networks. Over the deeper networks Geebs-Sigmoid does have lower latency than standard sigmoid indicating some learning is occurring. This disagreement with the MAIR and stagnation accuracy metrics is likely due to Geebs-Sigmoids smaller standard deviation across repeats rather than it actually out-performing Sigmoid.

Overall, from the MNIST tests, the results are inconclusive as to whether Geebs-Sigmoid substantially outperforms standard Sigmoid on shallower networks. However, it is clear that standard Sigmoid is more successful as the depth of the networks is increased.

At the present time it is not understood why Geebs-Sigmoid’s MAIR metric is substantially higher than Geebs-Tanh on shallower networks since they have relatively similar formulations. It is suspected to be related to Geebs-Sigmoid’s bounds of zero and one which match the MNIST one-hot classifications as opposed to Geebs-Tanh’s bounds of minus one and positive one. Geebs-Sigmoid’s poorer performance, compared to Geebs-Tanh, across deeper networks can be understood in terms of the criteria. The criteria are shown in *Tab. 1*:

Criteria	Geebs-Sigmoid	Geebs-Tanh	Geebs-ReLU
Non-Linearity	YES	YES	YES
Multi-Variable	YES	YES	YES
Intrinsic Dimension Preservation	YES	YES	YES
Extrinsic Dimension Preservation	YES	YES	YES
Spherical Symmetry	NO	YES	YES
Projection	YES	YES	YES
Identity Jacobian	YES	YES	NO
Centre at the Origin	NO	YES	YES
Bounded	YES	YES	NO

Table 1: Shows which of the criteria are fulfilled for Geebs-Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh.

It can be seen that Geebs-Sigmoid does not meet the centre at the origin nor the spherical symmetry criteria. The change in formulation between Geebs-Sigmoid and Geebs-Tanh is directly related to these criteria, so its poor performance must be due to their nonfulfillment. This gives direct empirical justification of the criteria. This test did not ascertain whether Geebs-Sigmoid performed better at its desired function of providing a blocking signal. Therefore, the following tests provide evidence whether Geebs-Sigmoid is effective at the purpose it was specifically tailored for.

5.3.2 Memory Testing: Long-Short-Term-Memory Networks

Geebs-Sigmoid was specifically designed to match standard Sigmoid's bounds such that it could be used in a blocking gate. A common usage of a blocking gate is within the Long-Short-Term-Memory network, the network providing the blocking signal and blocking gate operation are highlighted in red and yellow respectively in *Fig. 28*.

Figure 28: Displays an LSTM architecture [9]. This specific LSTM architecture is slightly modified to increase the number of fully connected layers shown in green and red. The purpose of this was to allow the network to learn more complicated data. A key for the meaning of symbols in this diagram is displayed in *Sec. 8.4* in *Fig. 43*

The networks are trained on an n length string of random numbers drawn uniformly from the interval $[0, 1]$. The purpose is for the network to memorise this string of random numbers. To ensure the network is utilising a time dependent mapping function as opposed to a simple mapping, the string of random numbers was rounded to one significant figure to ensure the sequential nature of the data was used.

The network training procedure is as follows: initialise the activations of the recurrent loop with random values drawn from a standard normal distribution. Then begin iterating through every element in the string of random numbers, performing a forward pass, then calculating the mean-squared error cost from the predicted next value in the sequence compared to the actual next value in the sequence. A parameter update is performed at every step using the Adam optimiser. Once iteration over the entire string is complete, overwrite the existing activations of the recurrent loop with random values drawn from a normal distribution matching the mean and standard deviation of that element of the recurrent activation values across the batch. Then begin iterative training along the string again. Repeating this process 200 times in total.

Batches are defined differently in this scenario, whereas usually the input data is a randomised sample from the dataset, here the input data is identical samples from the l^{th} element of the string across all the batches. How the batches differ is the activation of the recurrent loop, which as mentioned are initially drawn from a random standard normal distribution and later a normal distribution with mean and standard deviation matching each element in the activations of the recurrent loop.

Three different architectures were each tested 5 times per string length. The strings used were of lengths: 250, 500, 750 and 1000 elements. A new metric was also defined for the following tests: the *cost-inverse-gradient* (CIG). To calculate the CIG value requires a mean-squared-error cost value at every time step of training. These cost values are then raised to the power of minus one and least-squares linear regression is used to find the gradient of this data - the uncertainty should also be included in the regression model. The gradient found is the value for the CIG metric. The higher the CIG value, the faster the network approaches the correct value - so it is a measure of network learning speed.

The three architectures tested are variants of the architecture displayed in *Fig. 29*. They consist of a standard LSTM, displayed in *Fig. 28*, sandwiched between two fully connected layers. They differ by the activation functions used inside the standard LSTM.

Figure 29: Displays the "Standard-Standard" LSTM architecture. This model utilises the typical Sigmoid and Tanh activation functions in networks highlighted in green and also utilises the standard Sigmoid activation function in networks highlighted in red.

The first variant is identical to the one presented in *Fig. 29* and is named "Standard-Standard" reflecting the standard activation functions used in both the red labelled networks and the green labelled networks. The second variant is named "Standard-Geebs", where the red networks utilising the Sigmoid activation functions are instead replaced with Geebs-Sigmoid activation functions, whilst the networks shown in green use the standard activation functions shown in *Fig. 29*. Finally, the variant labelled "Geebs-Geebs" replaces all instances of the Sigmoid activation function in the red labelled networks with the Geebs-Sigmoid activation function and replaces all activation functions in the green labelled networks with the Geebs-Tanh activation function.

Results for the CIG metric are displayed in:

6 Discussion

6.1 More on the Origin-Centricity Postulate

6.1.1 Example of the Interpretations

In *Fig. 30*, the activation space of a made-up, trained, generative, classification network is drawn with a made-up dataset populating it. It is intended to show how we might interpret what the network is 'experiencing' at each layer. Real examples are shown in *Sec. 6.1.2*, but are more difficult to analyse.

With respect to the hidden layer, we might interpret that orange and purple mean roughly the same concept to that layer, but orange represents that concept more strongly. Yellow would be interpreted as representing the opposite property from orange and purple at various strengths. Red and green would be representing an entirely different meaning to orange and purple, with green representing a higher amount of that experience than red. In this dataset, there are no examples of the opposite experience of the red-green direction - but we could interpret its existence for that hidden layer nonetheless. Pink would be an example of a compound experience, it should be interpreted as representing both the red-green and orange-purple experiences simultaneously and strongly. There is no examples in the dataset of a weak version of this compound experience nor its opposite. With respect to the input layer, we might conclude that there are two primary experiences, since the manifold's intrinsic dimensionality is equal to two and the network would not be experiencing any opposite sensations.

Figure 30: This figure attempts to display the property-direction (PD) and signed-strength-scaling (SSS) interpretation in terms of a made-up data manifold. (Left) shows how the manifold might appear as raw data. (Right) shows the manifold at some layer in a classification network. The grey dotted arrows indicate the coordinate system of the manifold whilst the black lines are the coordinate system of activation space. The colours indicate the made-up classification.

As can be seen the 'primary meaning-basis' is difficult to determine and somewhat arbitrary. It does not need to be orthogonal either. For example pink could become a primary experience and instead red and green can be considered a compound experience. It is important to emphasise that this is an

interpretation of why the network organises manifolds as it does; only in certain circumstances, when alignment is expected between network and people, may it be used to predict a manifold distribution. Unfortunately, this does make the interpretations unfalsifiable as may be expected. It is also not intended to necessarily suggest that the network has any conscious awareness of these 'experiences'. It is all simply a method to rationalise a network's behaviour. As mentioned, it is a generalisation of existing interpretations. These generalised interpretations are intended to more closely follow and explain the observed manifold distributions. Now meanings do not have to be neuron-basis aligned, do not have to be orthogonal and there may be fewer meanings represented than the number of neurons encoding them.

6.1.2 Discussion of Property-Direction Hypothesis

The property-direction interpretation can also be predictive in certain circumstances leading to the property-direction hypothesis. For example, it would indicate that auto-encoders attempt to distribute all their data directionally since all the datapoints need to be isolated as all are qualitatively different for an auto-encoder as their data is not labelled by any group. Thus we should find the alike digits more diffusely around a general direction than a classification network which would be clustered more precisely towards specific directions. Different digits, with similar typography, should also be found close to similar directions for the auto-encoder, since they will contain similar components of specific meaning-basis-vectors. The classification network is expected to have more distinct directional separation, as the labelling of digits results in details about the digit's appearance being irrelevant. Since there are fewer properties, then fewer degrees-of-freedom are required for their representation. This results in a lower intrinsic dimension manifold, requiring fewer meaning-basis-vectors to span its volume. Hence, there are fewer directions necessitated. We would then expect the network to maximally separate these - producing an observed greater distinction between directions. The interpretation for an auto-encoder was particularly important as little human interference is imposed on the shape of the manifolds besides the data itself. Thus, their manifold distribution gives a better indication of the property-direction hypothesis for general neural networks - as auto-encoders may be considered to behave, and store data, more 'instinctively' for an artificial network.

This is tested in *Fig. 31* where a convolutional auto-encoder is used to recreate MNIST images, with 3 'pinch-neurons' (where 'pinch-neurons' are defined as the neurons at the narrowest layer of the auto-encoder). This is compared to a convolutional classification network with a 3-neuron layer situated in the 4th to last layer of the network. This hidden layer was chosen so that there was less human influence imposed on the manifold by the output layer needing to be interpretable. However, since it is an earlier layer, not all features may have been separated out yet. The MNIST test dataset is then passed through each of the networks and the activations of the pinch-neurons are stored for each example. This produces a set of 3-dimensional vectors. A 3D space is in-

sufficient to represent all the digit variants, so greater overlap between digits is expected compared to a larger network. The origin-centricity present in *Fig. 31* is induced by the Geesbs-Tanh activation function used at all layers in both networks. Therefore, the experiment only indicates whether the property-direction hypothesis is justified. The networks were also trained with a large amount of image noise to ensure the network generalised as opposed to memorised the entire dataset - the noise was also present on the test-set used to gather the final results.

Figure 31: Shows a representation of the distribution of the manifold at the pinch-layer of an auto-encoder (left) and classification network (right). It can be seen that the auto-encoder has a more diffuse directional correlation. Digits with similar typography are found closer together in the auto-encoder representation, such as '3', '5' and '8' as well as '4', '7' and '9'. In the classification network, the manifold can be seen to occupy only one hemisphere.

In *Fig. 31* it can be seen that datapoints representing the same MNIST digit are found together diffusely around a general direction for the auto-encoder, whereas datapoints of different digits are found at different directions as expected. This is despite the auto-encoder having no notion of a numerical digit, nor any form of labelling of the data. This distribution is a result of the appearance of the handwritten digits only. In addition, digits {'3', '5', '8'} are found in close proximity as well as {'4', '7', '9'}. Typographically, these digits appear similar to humans as well - especially when including a barred-seven. This indicates some alignment between how artificial and biological networks classify patterns and represent them.

These tests were repeated for 32 pinch-neurons so that the networks have sufficient space to represent the properties. This test should give a better indication of the validity of the property-direction hypothesis. In *Fig. 32* a cosine-similarity matrix is presented for an auto-encoder and classification network. The similarities are found between every permutation of 32-dimensional vectors produced in the forward pass of the test-set. These similarities are then grouped by digit permutation types in order to determine the mean and standard deviation.

Auto-Encoder										Classification Network										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
0	0.750524	-0.450824	0.130434	0.030131	-0.040132	0.130234	0.040131	-0.040131	-0.110131	0	0.750524	0.200131	-0.010131	0.170131	0.040131	0.160131	0.200131	0.170131	0.200131	0.200131
1	-0.200131	0.750524	0.030131	0.030131	0.030131	0.040132	0.030131	0.070131	0.140131	1	0.200131	0.750524	0.170131	0.030131	0.130131	0.140131	0.140131	0.140131	0.140131	0.140131
2	0.130434	-0.030131	0.750524	0.130131	-0.040132	0.030131	0.030131	-0.110131	0.030131	2	0.010131	0.170131	0.030131	0.750524	-0.010131	-0.010131	-0.010131	0.170131	-0.130131	-0.130131
3	0.030131	0.030131	0.130434	0.750524	-0.040132	0.130234	-0.040131	0.070131	-0.040131	3	0.170131	0.030131	0.130131	0.010131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131
4	-0.040132	0.030131	-0.040132	-0.040132	0.750524	0.040131	0.130234	0.130131	0.030131	4	0.040131	0.130131	-0.010131	0.040131	0.010131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131
5	0.130234	-0.040132	0.030131	0.030131	0.040131	0.750524	0.030131	0.030131	0.030131	5	0.040131	0.130131	-0.010131	0.040131	0.010131	0.130131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131
6	0.040131	0.030131	0.030131	0.030131	0.040131	0.030131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131	6	0.040131	0.130131	0.130131	0.030131	0.030131	0.130131	0.130131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131
7	-0.040132	0.070131	-0.110131	-0.110131	0.130131	0.040131	0.030131	0.750524	0.030131	7	0.070131	0.040131	-0.130131	-0.040131	0.070131	-0.040131	-0.130131	0.750524	0.130131	0.130131
8	0.030131	0.070131	0.030131	0.030131	0.030131	0.030131	0.130131	0.030131	0.750524	8	0.030131	0.040131	0.130131	0.040131	0.030131	0.130131	0.130131	-0.130131	0.750524	0.130131
9	-0.110131	0.140131	-0.130131	-0.040131	0.030131	0.040131	0.030131	0.030131	0.130131	9	0.130131	0.130131	-0.130131	0.030131	0.030131	0.130131	0.130131	0.130131	-0.130131	0.750524

Figure 32: Cosine-similarity between the average 32-dimensional direction of different digits for the an auto-encoder (left) and classification network (right). Where -1 represents exactly opposite directions and +1 represents exactly equal direction, 0 is orthogonal. Colour coded by mean similarity where green is closer to +1, red -1 and 0 orthogonal.

The similarities between alike digits for the auto-encoder are valued at about 0.4. This indicates how the datapoints are diffusely grouped together but still tend to occupy their own directions. It also shows that most different digit permutations are close to orthogonal, indicating that properties we would also consider distinct are found in different directions. For a classification network, the alike digit similarities were expected to be higher than the auto-encoder and this is observed as the similarities are valued at about 0.7. The different-digit permutations are unexpectedly larger and more positive than predicted for the classification network. In the classification network the digits '2' and '7' are the most distinctly separated. Perhaps this is an indication that the 4th to last network layer is responsible for specifically determining these digits. The test set accuracy was determined to be 92.7% for this model indicating it is well trained. Further tests, at different layers, would need to be performed to be conclusive. It can be seen that the permutations of particularly '4', '7' and '9' (and less so digits '3' and '5') show close similarities for the auto-encoder as in agreement with the 3D visualisation.

As stated, many of the different digit permutations for the auto-encoder are close to orthogonal and these distinctions between different digits are the result of the auto-encoder's interpretation based solely on digit typography. The digits '2', '7' and the collective other digits, also appear close to orthogonal for the classification network. These findings are expected from the postulate - also making the manifold close to origin-centric.

6.1.3 Qualia and Activation Space

According to the property-direction and signed-strength-scaling interpretations, it may be reasoned that if a datapoint is initially at the origin then it should remain at the origin as meaning cannot be derived from nothing. This is correct with respect to a particular meaning-basis. However, each layer of the neural network establishes a different meaning-basis. A thought experiment can be used as a demonstration: an opposite direction in activation space is thought

to represent an opposite meaning from the perspective of a network layer. In the example of a classification network for solving handwritten equations, each layer produces an increasingly abstract meaning-basis. For example with respect to the input layer, a white '1' is presented on a black background. The stimulus which corresponds to an opposite direction on the input layer would be a black '1' on a white background. However, deeper into the network, where properties of the image are more abstractly represented, then a stimulus which produces an opposite direction compared to the initial stimulus may be a white '-1' on a black background - this is more abstract as the opposite stimuli is a notion from mathematics not simply a negative stimuli. Stimuli with opposing meanings can be found by optimising input activations to produce a particular network activation and its opposite. This may lead to further insight on what properties neural networks express. This can also be applied analogously to human cognition.

We propose this is a model for why a negative-colour is seen after dazzling one's retina. The original coloured light stimulus is a vector in activation space and neuron desensitisation is described as the addition of a vector in the opposite direction which slowly increases in magnitude. Eventually a resultant vector is formed with a much smaller magnitude, cancelling out the initial stimulus. When the initial stimulus is then removed the vector sum becomes just the negative compensation vector, causing a resultant vector in the opposite direction producing an effective stimulus and the negative-colour is perceived. This is perceived as a change in colour from red to cyan if initially dazzled with red light, this interpretation would suggest that one of the perceptory layers in the brain has constructed a meaning basis in which red is of opposite meaning to cyan. The vectors referenced would need to be time averaged due to biological neurons spiking as opposed to prolonged activation. In addition, the direction and magnitude must be taken from the centre of the space in this case due to the biological step-function not being centred on the typical origin - this is acceptable as biological network operations may not be origin-centric such as in the artificial analogs. A coordinate transformation could also be performed treating over-firing neurons as *+ve* and under-firing neurons as *-ve*. The concept of the vector addition also explains the chimerical colours. Hyperbolic orange is a further scaling in the orange direction by the signed-strength-scaling hypothesis, likewise with stygian blue and self-luminous red. Perhaps these latter two colours are represented in directions not ordinarily spanned by the manifold, in later network layers, so appear as a entirely different experience according to the property-direction hypothesis.

Specifically, the property-direction hypothesis explains why a different colour is experienced entirely. This is because the resultant stimulus is of nearly the same magnitude as the initial stimulus, but points in a different directions so is perceived strongly as a different type experience. It is seen as the distinct cyan rather than a dulled sense of red. Normally the phenomena is described due to the under-firing of the previously over-stimulate neurons in white light: thus when red light is subtracted from white light it appears cyan. It is unclear, in this explanation, why the brain interprets this as the different colour cyan

with a similar vibrance to the initial colour. In the property-direction case, the brain has learnt to assign the sensation of viewing cyan to that opposite direction. Moreover, the local visual field where dazzling occurred also remains distinct even in darkness which is also explained with the property-direction hypothesis. This red-dazzling example also indicates how networks may have different meaning-basis at different layers. The abstract notions of red and cyan are not necessarily considered opposites to our conscious selves. Yet, qualia is dependent upon the less abstract perception process which has a meaning-basis in which red and cyan are considered as opposites.

This is a return to the aforementioned qualia interpretation of activation space - although it is in question whether an arbitrary network exhibits any awareness or purposeful manipulation on the distribution of these datapoints required for the usual definition of an experience of qualia. In addition, these properties may have no significant meaning to the observer, only to the network, as discussed. Yet, there may be examples where correlation between human qualia and network meaning-basis are expected such as in networks processing labelled or visual data. This was seen in the previous auto-encoder where the digit's specific typography resulted in its datapoint being found in a general direction. In addition, these meaning-basis-vectors might be what applications of primary component analysis (PCA) [14] to neural networks attempt to ascertain - a certain direction which represents one property in the data. Though PCA works by analysis of the directional variance of the manifold. There are meaning-vectors between every permutations of all data points, however at each layer the network will only express a particular meaning-basis which it considers important and it is these meaning-basis-vectors which are expected to be origin-centric and transformed to be approximately linear such that they increase in strength along one direction only as the magnitude increases. Although, it is unclear whether the meaning-basis-vectors are of unit length. If not, the relation between magnitude and property strength may be direction dependent.

6.1.4 Generative Functions

As mentioned generative transformations are those defined by the increase in the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold from before to after the transformation. For fully-connected networks (with more output neurons than input neurons) this is problematic as they instead embed the manifold in an extrinsically higher dimensional space, yet the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold remains unchanged and cannot be increased by a solely linear operation. In fact, a function which produces an integer-generative transformations (those which increase the intrinsic dimensionality by an integer value) are actually impossible by definition of a function as require more input variables than available to the function. However, pseudo-generative and apparent-generative transformations are still possible. Apparent-generative transformations can occur when a manifold is sufficiently sparse that it appears to increase in intrinsic dimension, examples of this may include deconvolutional networks such as image up-scaling where detail appears to be restored to a pixelated image.

Pseudo-generative processes rely on fractals. One can imagine embedding a \mathbb{R}^N manifold, non-origin centrally, in a \mathbb{R}^M space where $M > N$. Taking the image of this space by an activation function, causes slight bending to the embedded manifold. Repeating this many times, in a reformative process, can cause folding of the original embedding - concertinaing the manifold into layers. Repeating this to infinity yields a fractal manifold with an intrinsic dimensionality greater than what it started with, thus generation has effectively taken place. This process is particularly effective in sparse manifolds where the notion of intrinsic dimensionality is less clearly defined. *Fig. 33* outlines this process graphically. Consequently, the bending of straight lines by an activation function, when they don't pass through the origin, can be useful in some circumstances - it is likely a network will learn to exploit this if needs be. However, we would expect these activation function criteria to be most applicable to reformative and abstractive network structures and potentially perform poorly on networks intended for generation due to the reduced distortion of straight lines compared to other activation functions.

Figure 33: (Left) shows a manifold with an intrinsic dimensionality of \mathbb{R} embedded in a space \mathbb{R}^2 but crucially not through the origin. Progressing rightwards shows taking the image of that manifold through many activation functions. In the limit of infinite passes through an activation function, the manifold increases to an effective intrinsic dimensionality of \mathbb{R}^2 . Note, that this is a fractal so must pass through fractional intrinsic dimensions as it is slowly folded [7].

The abstract notion of apparent or pseudo-generative transformations may be considered an explanation for imagination in the brain. In effect, it may be argued that a simple descriptive sentence is of lower intrinsic dimensionality than an imagined visual-spatial scene. Yet, a simple sentence is enough to seed the brain to produce such a visual-spatial imagined scene. So perhaps this is an example of a generative neural process. However, it may be argued that this imagination draws on past experience such that it is not just a function of just the sentence. Yet, with a sparse manifold due to a finite number of experiences we could describe this using a pseudo-generative process. In effect, if experience 'A' led to neural output 'B' and experience 'C' led to neural output 'D', then due to the non-linear nature of neural networks experiences 'A' and 'C' experienced simultaneously do not lead to a neural output 'BD' instead they lead to output 'E'. This could be a rough, working model, for novel thought when 'E' is encoded in a direction not previously represented in the sparse manifold. A novel combination of existing meaning-basis-vectors into a new 'original' type of experience. This is according again to the property-direction hypothesis, stating neural representation of 'B', 'D' and 'E' (such that $B \neq D \neq$

E) are encoded at different directions and are therefore different 'experiences' for the network. This also means the manifold has been extended into a new region in the direction of 'E' where it was not before - thus this model may be sometimes considered a pseudo-generative process as the manifold slightly increases in intrinsic dimensionality if the direction was not previously spanned by the meaning-basis.

7 Background

7.1 Generative-Friendly Activation Function

In *Sec. 6.1.4* pseudo-generative transformations are described in terms of folding manifolds. An activation function could be designed such that it meets all the criteria whilst causing increased folding of lines which do not intersect the origin. A starting proposal for this function is Geesbs-Sin: $\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = (1 + \alpha \sin |\vec{x}|) \hat{x}$ which causes increased folding of off-centre manifolds and $0 < \alpha$ is a scaling factor for those distortions. Figure 34 displays this function. Despite being unbounded this function will not suffer from the 'escaping non-linearity problem' since the non-linearity is not local. This function will remain theoretical as is out-of-scope for this paper and it could be vastly improved.

Figure 34: (Left) Shows a \mathbb{R}^2 input space, with concentric circles centred about the origin in black, sets of parallel lines in red and blue. Whilst in green there are 2 lines of the form $y = mx$. (Right) shows the image of the input space through a Geesbs-Sin mapping. It can be seen that off-centre lines are folded.

7.2 Geeb's ReLU Derivation

Geesbs-ReLU was intended to be an alternative to Leaky-ReLU. Leaky-ReLU is defined by two linear regions of gradients $0 \leq \alpha < 1$ and 1: $F(x) = \max(\alpha x, x)$. These linear regions are separated by a directional boundary which acts as the function's non-linearity. If $\alpha = 0$ the function is instead just referred to as ReLU. Figure 35 shows the Leaky-ReLU mapping and its derivative.

Figure 35: (Left) Shows the leaky-ReLU mapping for $\alpha = 0.1$, this mapping is applied elementwise to vectors. (Centre) shows the derivative of leaky-ReLU with respect to input x . It can be seen that it has two linear regions separated by a non-linear step function at $x=0$. (Right) For the new ReLU function to be spherically-symmetric it must have a derivative similar to that shown on the right, with two linear regions of 1 when $|x| > \beta$ and α when $|x| < \beta$. $\beta = 2$ and $\alpha = 0.1$ were arbitrarily chosen for this demonstration.

Where $0 \leq \beta$ is the offset parameter. By integrating the proposed derivative sketched in *Fig. 35* and ensuring the spherical symmetry criteria is satisfied for the resulting vector function, *Eqn. 34* is obtained:

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = (\max(\alpha(|\vec{x}| - \beta), |\vec{x}| - \beta) + \beta) \hat{x} \quad (34)$$

This function satisfies the non-linearity criterion (seen at $|\vec{x}| = \beta$), spherical-symmetric criterion (and multivariate by implication), Intrinsic-Extrinsic-dimension criterion, origin-centric and projection. However, it fails to meet the unbounded criterion (by definition of a ReLU), gradient-of-one and most importantly the continuity criterion. The latter is simply resolved by an addition of a $\alpha\beta$ term shown in *Eqn. 35*

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = (\max(\alpha(|\vec{x}| - \beta), |\vec{x}| - \beta) + \alpha\beta) \hat{x} \quad (35)$$

This function was initially tested and found to under-perform and this was found to be due to the 'escaping non-linearity problem' discussed in *Sec. 2.2.1*. It appeared the manifold is only one of the two linear regions for a given network, since it did not span across both; the essential non-linear effects disappeared. This resulted in poor performance. Fine tuning of α and β did not prove successful either; it appeared the manifold shifted to counteract their change. In effect, if β was chosen to be equal to the mean magnitude of points in the manifold upon initialisation, to ensure the manifold was initially distributed across the non-linearity, the network always then shifted the manifold away from the non-linearity returning to a linear regime. It was thought that the non-smoothness of the function caused a 'pushing' effect on the manifold. These parameters were also changed so that the network could control them and they could be updated by backpropagation - this was unsuccessful too. Therefore, the decision to adapt the function so that it was smooth was taken - in an effort to reduce the 'escaping non-linearity problem'. *Figure 36* and *Eqn. 36* demonstrates continuous derivative required for a smooth function.

$$\frac{dF(x)}{dx} = \alpha + \frac{(1 - \alpha) \left(1 + \tanh\left(\frac{(|x| - \beta)}{\delta}\right)\right)}{2} \quad (36)$$

Figure 36: Shows the desired gradient of a smooth analogue of Eqn. 35. In this example $\alpha = 0.1$, $\beta = 3$ and $\delta = 0.1$ where δ is a new parameter for the smoothing of the derivative: $0 < \delta$.

Once again, by integrating the expression shown in Eqn. 36 an activation function can be obtained with the desired properties. This activation function is shown in Eqn. 37:

$$F(x) = \left(\frac{(1 - \alpha)}{2} \delta \ln \left(\frac{\cosh\left(\frac{|x| - \beta}{\delta}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{\beta}{\delta}\right)} \right) + \frac{(1 + \alpha)}{2} |x| \right) \frac{x}{|x|} \quad (37)$$

Which in vector form becomes Eqn: 38:

$$\vec{F}(\vec{x}) = \left(\frac{(1 - \alpha)}{2} \delta \ln \left(\frac{\cosh\left(\frac{|\vec{x}| - \beta}{\delta}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{\beta}{\delta}\right)} \right) + \frac{(1 + \alpha)}{2} |\vec{x}| \right) \hat{x} \quad (38)$$

As $\delta \rightarrow 0$, it can be shown that Eqn. 38 becomes equal to Eqn. 35. As described in Sec. 3.3 this formulation can be further simplified with precalculation of constant terms and approximation of the $\ln \cosh$ function.

8 Appendices

8.1 MNIST: Fully-Connected Networks Gees-Tanh Appendix

Figure 37: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 2 (Left), 3 (Center), 4 (Right)) trained on MNIST using Sigmoid, Tanh and Gees-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Gees-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Figure 38: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 5 (Left), 6 (Center), 7 (Right)) trained on MNIST using Sigmoid, Tanh and Gees-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Gees-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Figure 39: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 5 (Left), 6 (Center), 7 (Right)) trained on MNIST using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geebs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Geebs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Number of Layers	Geebs-Sigmoid	Geebs-Tanh	Sigmoid	Tanh
2	0.26 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02
3	2.40 ± 0.32	1.64 ± 0.05	0.67 ± 0.09	0.43 ± 0.04
4	9.81 ± 0.94	3.23 ± 0.12	0.98 ± 0.19	1.07 ± 0.09
5	2.68 ± 0.67	4.68 ± 0.26	1.05 ± 0.06	1.33 ± 0.20
6	1.17 ± 0.08	5.62 ± 0.19	1.17 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.49
7	1.17 ± 0.09	7.18 ± 0.21	1.45 ± 0.31	0.99 ± 0.38
8	1.17 ± 0.10	8.23 ± 0.20	1.20 ± 0.13	0.66 ± 0.07
9	1.14 ± 0.08	9.91 ± 0.12	1.14 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.02
10	1.11 ± 0.07	10.58 ± 0.84	1.22 ± 0.31	0.52 ± 0.01

Table 2: Maximum-Accuracy-Improvement-Rate of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

Number of Layers	Geebs-Sigmoid	Geebs-Tanh	Sigmoid	Tanh
2	83.13 ± 0.18	83.75 ± 0.14	81.82 ± 5.97	53.32 ± 0.73
3	84.27 ± 0.46	83.28 ± 0.26	82.81 ± 9.20	18.57 ± 2.83
4	82.41 ± 0.86	84.25 ± 0.26	83.41 ± 8.97	27.79 ± 0.82
5	15.01 ± 14.24	85.44 ± 0.34	85.04 ± 10.38	17.59 ± 7.18
6	11.31 ± 0.32	88.36 ± 0.43	82.08 ± 15.23	13.78 ± 4.42
7	11.34 ± 0.29	90.56 ± 0.39	81.21 ± 11.50	12.22 ± 5.31
8	11.25 ± 0.42	91.68 ± 0.40	80.75 ± 7.17	22.23 ± 6.21
9	11.33 ± 0.33	92.48 ± 0.25	76.40 ± 13.80	20.41 ± 1.08
10	11.26 ± 0.49	93.03 ± 0.23	74.43 ± 15.50	17.33 ± 1.10

Table 3: Stagnation accuracies of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

Number of Layers	Geebs-Sigmoid	Geebs-Tanh	Sigmoid	Tanh
2	290.00 ± 18.06	197.00 ± 49.73	369.00 ± 108.30	195.67 ± 41.71
3	125.67 ± 8.26	14.00 ± 4.32	69.67 ± 13.60	3425.00 ± 4648.53
4	297.67 ± 213.53	7.33 ± 0.47	56.33 ± 35.57	205.33 ± 43.44
5	146.33 ± 37.81	6.00 ± 0.82	114.33 ± 72.37	171.67 ± 102.16
6	204.67 ± 94.91	3.67 ± 0.47	919.67 ± 723.53	166.67 ± 105.31
7	186.67 ± 52.45	2.00 ± 0.82	558.67 ± 396.95	285.00 ± 127.88
8	179.67 ± 13.52	2.67 ± 0.47	1370.67 ± 1449.38	244.33 ± 156.64
9	153.33 ± 66.25	1.67 ± 0.47	4042.00 ± 3195.10	95.33 ± 18.57
10	110.33 ± 15.08	1.33 ± 0.47	5284.33 ± 3350.29	122.33 ± 25.72

Table 4: Latencies of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

8.2 CIFAR: Fully-Connected Networks Geebs-Tanh Appendix

Figure 40: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 2 (Left), 3 (Center), 4 (Right)) trained on CIFAR using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geebs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Geebs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Figure 41: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 5 (Left), 6 (Center), 7 (Right)) trained on CIFAR using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geebs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Geebs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Figure 42: Displays the accuracies per epoch for fully-connected networks of depth 5 (Left), 6 (Center), 7 (Right)) trained on CIFAR using Sigmoid, Tanh and Geesbs-Tanh. Bold-coloured lines in blue, red and green represent the average accuracies of Geesbs-Tanh, Sigmoid and Tanh respectively over 10 repeats. The shaded area represents the mean accuracy plus and minus one standard deviation of accuracy across the 30 repeats. Very faint lines indicate the accuracy for each individual repeat.

Number of Layers	Tanh	Sigmoid	Geesbs-Tanh
2	0.68 ± 0.06	0.25 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.01
3	0.39 ± 0.12	0.69 ± 0.04	1.27 ± 0.24
4	1.33 ± 0.31	0.88 ± 0.15	1.72 ± 0.07
5	2.15 ± 0.85	0.81 ± 0.04	2.56 ± 0.17
6	2.49 ± 0.90	0.92 ± 0.06	2.19 ± 0.37
7	1.72 ± 0.37	1.14 ± 0.09	2.05 ± 0.15
8	1.56 ± 0.31	1.12 ± 0.17	1.75 ± 0.33
9	0.71 ± 0.09	1.40 ± 0.14	2.01 ± 0.40
10	0.45 ± 0.04	1.47 ± 0.12	2.64 ± 0.63

Table 5: Maximum-Accuracy-Improvement-Rate of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on CIFAR.

Number of Layers	Tanh	Sigmoid	Geesbs-Tanh
2	12.65 ± 1.96	14.19 ± 2.70	40.66 ± 0.27
3	10.03 ± 0.17	33.61 ± 5.13	38.93 ± 0.73
4	13.10 ± 3.08	35.00 ± 4.99	37.14 ± 0.78
5	13.45 ± 4.04	33.60 ± 4.76	35.72 ± 1.06
6	11.23 ± 2.13	29.64 ± 7.88	43.09 ± 2.64
7	10.86 ± 1.75	27.83 ± 8.31	44.80 ± 0.56
8	10.29 ± 0.92	26.53 ± 9.33	45.64 ± 0.71
9	10.06 ± 0.82	31.16 ± 8.36	46.17 ± 0.72
10	9.83 ± 0.32	28.83 ± 11.59	46.55 ± 0.59

Table 6: Stagnation accuracies of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on CIFAR.

Number of Layers	Tanh	Sigmoid	Geebs-Tanh
2	3586.33 ± 4537.15	9999.00 ± 0.00	56.00 ± 3.56
3	9999.00 ± 0.00	3498.67 ± 4596.90	10.67 ± 0.94
4	3500.00 ± 4595.69	6037.67 ± 2927.68	8.67 ± 0.47
5	880.67 ± 197.98	2469.67 ± 3238.55	5.67 ± 0.47
6	5279.00 ± 3340.23	8008.67 ± 2814.76	4.33 ± 0.47
7	9999.00 ± 0.00	9999.00 ± 0.00	4.00 ± 0.00
8	9999.00 ± 0.00	6680.33 ± 4693.30	4.00 ± 0.82
9	9999.00 ± 0.00	6734.00 ± 4617.41	4.67 ± 1.70
10	6724.00 ± 4631.55	9999.00 ± 0.00	4.00 ± 0.82

Table 7: Latencies of activation functions across fully-connected networks of different depths tested on CIFAR.

8.3 MNIST: Convolutional Networks Geebs-ReLU Appendix

Number of Layers	LeakyReLU	ReLU	GeebsReLU	GeebsTanh
0	0.91 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.07	2.27 ± 0.23
1	0.83 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.05	0.87 ± 0.04	2.03 ± 0.19
2	0.97 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.05	0.93 ± 0.12	2.18 ± 0.19
3	0.93 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.05	0.93 ± 0.08	2.71 ± 0.56
4	0.95 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.10	0.98 ± 0.10	2.55 ± 0.19
5	0.97 ± 0.12	0.97 ± 0.10	1.01 ± 0.13	2.94 ± 0.84

Table 8: Maximum-Accuracy-Improvement-Rate of activation functions across convolutional networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

Number of Layers	LeakyReLU	ReLU	GeebsReLU	GeebsTanh
0	86.03 ± 2.04	77.41 ± 3.04	85.92 ± 1.61	97.59 ± 1.62
1	85.05 ± 1.83	76.47 ± 4.33	85.64 ± 2.40	97.87 ± 0.39
2	84.66 ± 3.46	73.70 ± 5.98	85.60 ± 2.84	97.93 ± 0.44
3	85.26 ± 2.89	71.01 ± 7.23	85.55 ± 2.91	97.94 ± 0.41
4	84.61 ± 2.80	68.97 ± 8.62	85.10 ± 2.54	97.95 ± 0.45
5	84.44 ± 2.48	68.10 ± 8.41	84.54 ± 2.51	98.13 ± 0.42

Table 9: Stagnation accuracies of activation functions across convolutional networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

Number of Layers	Leaky-ReLU	ReLU	Geebs-ReLU	Geebs-Tanh
0	224.67 ± 62.96	175.33 ± 48.00	141.33 ± 62.40	182.33 ± 59.57
1	359.67 ± 124.27	269.00 ± 88.74	236.33 ± 12.26	243.67 ± 161.54
2	201.67 ± 95.51	434.67 ± 297.68	188.33 ± 47.22	340.00 ± 211.78
3	243.00 ± 39.06	188.33 ± 38.14	174.33 ± 44.39	156.00 ± 31.19
4	191.00 ± 37.50	271.33 ± 187.24	121.00 ± 41.21	181.00 ± 39.86
5	170.33 ± 20.17	214.67 ± 74.39	140.00 ± 31.38	158.00 ± 6.48

Table 10: Learning Latencies of activation functions across convolutional networks of different depths tested on MNIST.

8.4 LSTM Gees-Sigmoid Appendix

Gees Diagrammatic System

Figure 43: This displays a proposed system to represent neural networks architectures with a consistent and concise diagrammatic system. It has taken inspiration from many other diagrams displaying network architectures but inconsistent representations prevail through all these diagrams potentially making them troublesome to understand. With this unified system any arbitrary network can be displayed in a simple, intuitive manner. Although, this preliminary system is not believed to be extensive and amendments will need to be considered. An example of a network drawn using this system is shown in *Fig. 28*.

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